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SHARQ FALSAFASI

ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA MEHNAT KODEKSINING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada mehnat erkinligi har kimning mehnat qilishga bo‘lgan o‘z qobiliyatlarini tasarruf etish, ularni qonun bilan taqiqlanmagan har qanday shaklda amalga oshirish, mashg‘ulot turini, kasbni va mutaxassislikni, ish joyini hamda mehnat sharoitlarini erkin tanlash huquqini yoritib o‘tgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Kodeks, Prinsip, Shartnoma, Diplomantik, Konsullik, Yagona milliy mehnat tizimi.

Аннотация: В данной статье под свободой труда понимается право каждого распоряжаться своими способностями к труду, осуществлять их в любой, не запрещенной законом форме, свободно выбирать вид обучения, профессию и специальность, место работы и трудовую деятельность. Условия прошли

Ключевые слова: Кодекс, Принцип, Соглашение, Дипломатический, Консульский, Единая национальная система труда.

Abstract: in this article, freedom of labor describes the right of everyone to dispose of his abilities to work, to exercise them in any form that is not prohibited by law, to freely choose the type of training, profession and specialty, workplace and working conditions. Passed

Key words: code, principle, agreement, diplomatic, consular, unified national labor system.

Mehnat Kodeksida xodimlar, ish beruvchilar va davlat manfaatlarining muvozanatini ta‘minlash hamda ularni muvofiqlashtirish asosida yakka tartibdagi mehnatga oid munosabatlarni va ular bilan bevosita bog‘liq bo‘lgan ijtimoiy munosabatlarni tartibga soladi.

Ushbu mehnat Kodeksning asosiy vazifalari quyidagilardan iborat:

xodimlar mehnat huquqlari va erkinliklarining, shu jumladan mehnat qilishga, erkin ish tanlashga, adolatli va xavfsiz mehnat sharoitlariga hamda ishsizlikdan himoyalanihga bo‘lgan huquqining davlat kafolatlarini belgilash;

ish beruvchilarning kadrlarni tanlash, joy-joyiga qo'yish va samarali mehnat jarayonini tashkil etish sohasidagi huquqlari amalga oshirilishini ta'minlash;
mehnat sohasida ijtimoiy sheriklikni rag'batlantirish va rivojlantirish;
xodimlar va ish beruvchilarning huquqlari hamda qonuniy manfaatlarini himoya qilinishini ta'minlash;

mehnat bozorining samarali faoliyat ko'rsatishiga ko'maklashish.

Mehnat erkinligi har kimning mehnat qilishga bo'lgan o'z qobiliyatlarini tasarruf etish, ularni qonun bilan taqiqlanmagan har qanday shaklda amalga oshirish, mashg'ulot turini, kasbni va mutaxassislikni, ish joyini hamda mehnat sharoitlarini erkin tanlash huquqini anglatadi.

Ushbu mehnat Kodeksida xodimlar va ish beruvchilar vakillarining jamoaviy muzokaralar olib borishga, jamoa kelishuvlarini hamda jamoa shartnomasini tuzishga bo'lgan huquqini mustahkamlaydi [1].

Yakka tartibdagi mehnatga oid munosabatlarga muvofiq mehnat erkinligi mehnat shartnomasi erkinligida namoyon bo'lib, bu quyidagilarni anglatadi:

xodimlar va ish beruvchilarning mehnat shartnomasini tuzishdagi erkinligini. Xodimni va ish beruvchini mehnat shartnomasini tuzishga majburlashga yo'l qo'yilmaydi. Ish beruvchi xodim bilan mehnat shartnomasini ushbu Kodeksda, qonunda yoki ixtiyoriy ravishda olingan majburiyatda ish beruvchining shartnoma tuzish majburiyati nazarda tutilgan hollarda tuzishi shart;

mehnat shartnomasining shartnomaviy (asosiy va qo'shimcha) shartlarini ushbu shartnoma taraflarining kelishuviga ko'ra belgilashni;

mehnat shartnomasini xodim va ish beruvchi o'rtasidagi kelishuvga ko'ra o'zgartirish imkoniyatini;

har qanday mehnat shartnomasini ushbu shartnoma taraflarining kelishuviga ko'ra istalgan vaqtda bekor qilish imkoniyatini;

Xodimning ushbu mehnat kodeksda belgilangan tartibda mehnat shartnomasini o'z tashabbusi bilan bekor qilish huquqini;

ish beruvchining xodim bilan tuzilgan mehnat shartnomasini ushbu Kodeksda mehnat shartnomasini bekor qilish uchun nazarda tutilgan asoslar mavjud bo'lganda va belgilangan tartibga rioya etilgan holda o'z tashabbusi bilan bekor qilish huquqini;

ushbu Kodeksda yoki boshqa qonunda belgilangan hollarda, mehnat shartnomasida uni bekor qilishning qo'shimcha asoslarini nazarda tutish imkoniyatini.

Majburiy mehnat taqiqlanadi.

Majburiy mehnat biror-bir jismoniy shaxsdan jazoni qo'llash tahdidi ostida talab etiladigan, bajarilishi uchun ushbu shaxs ixtiyoriy ravishda o'z xizmatlarini taklif qilmagan har qanday ishni yoki xizmatni anglatadi. Jazo deganda jismoniy shaxsning ixtiyoriy roziligi mavjud bo'lmagani holda, ushbu shaxsga nisbatan uni mehnat faoliyatini amalga oshirishga majbur qiladigan har qanday moddiy, jismoniy yoki ruhiy ta'sir choralarini qo'llash yoki qo'llash tahdidi tushuniladi[2].

Majburiy mehnat:

harbiy xususiyatga ega bo'lgan ishlarni yoki "Umumiy harbiy majburiyat va harbiy xizmat to'g'risida"gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuni asosida muqobil xizmatni o'tash bilan bog'liq ishlarni bajarishni;

bajarilishiga favqulodda yoki harbiy holat joriy etilishi sabab bo'ladigan ishni;

sud hukmlarini ijro etish chog'ida qonunchilikka rioya etilishi uchun mas'ul bo'lgan davlat organlari nazorati ostida sudning qonuniy kuchga kirgan hukmi bo'yicha jazo sifatida bajariladigan ishni o'z ichiga olmaydi.

Mehnat kodeksi bo'yicha quyidagilar yakka tartibdagi mehnat nizosining ko'rib chiqilishi uchun sudga murojaat qilish huquqiga ega:

- 1) xodim yoki kasaba uyushmasi qo'mitasi;
- 2) Davlat mehnat inspeksiyasining mansabdor shaxslari;
- 3) ish beruvchi, u mehnat nizolari bo'yicha komissiyaning qaroridan norozi bo'lganda, shuningdek o'ziga xodim tomonidan yetkazilgan moddiy zararining o'rnini qoplash haqidagi nizolar bo'yicha;
- 4) qonunchilikda belgilangan tartibda adliya organlari;
- 5) prokuror.

Mehnat kodeksi 34 bob, 7 bo'lim, 581 moddadan iborat va 30-apreldan kuchga kiradi.

Mehnat kodeksining 217-moddasida haq to'lanadigan yillik mehnat ta'tili kamida 21 kalendar kun bo'lishi kerak deyilyapti. Kodeksning 220-moddasida xodimlarga bir tashkilot yoki tarmoqdagi har 5 yil uchun davomiyligi 2 kalendar kun bo'lgan, biroq jami 8 kalendar kundan ko'p bo'lmagan qo'shimcha mehnat ta'tili berilishi aytilyapti. Qolaversa, 219-moddada qonunchilikda, jamoa kelishuvi, jamoa shartnomasi, ichki hujjatlar, mehnat shartnomasida nazarda tutilgan boshqa qo'shimcha mehnat ta'tili ham berilishi mumkinligi ko'zda tutilyapti^[3].

Quyidagi yakka tartibdagi mehnat nizolari bevosita sudda ko'rib chiqiladi:

- 1) agar xodimning ish joyida mehnat nizolari bo'yicha komissiya tuzilmagan bo'lsa;
- 2) mehnat shartnomasini bekor qilish asoslaridan qat'i nazar, ishga tiklash to'g'risidagi, mehnat shartnomasini bekor qilish sanasini va asoslari ta'rifini o'zgartirish haqidagi, majburiy progul yoki kam haq to'lanadigan ish bajarilgan vaqt uchun haq to'lash to'g'risidagi;
- 3) xodimga mehnatda mayib bo'lganligi yoki kasb kasalligi tufayli yetkazilgan ziyonning o'rnini yoxud xodimning mol-mulkiga yetkazilgan moddiy zararining o'rnini ish beruvchi tomonidan qoplash haqidagi;
- 4) ish beruvchi tomonidan xodimga yetkazilgan ma'naviy ziyonni kompensatsiya qilish to'g'risidagi;
- 5) ishga qabul qilish rad etilganligi haqidagi;
- 6) ish beruvchi tomonidan kasaba uyushmasi qo'mitasi bilan kelishilgan holda oldindan hal etilgan masalalar yuzasidan;
- 7) xodimlar va ish beruvchi jismoniy shaxslar o'rtasida yuzaga keladigan;

8) o'zini mehnat qilish va mashg'ulotlar sohasida kamsitilishga uchragan deb hisoblayotgan shaxslarning;

9) xodim tomonidan ish beruvchiga yetkazilgan moddiy zararining o'rnini qoplash haqidagi.

Yakka tartibdagi mehnat nizolari, ushbu moddaning [birinchi qismida](#) sanab o'tilganlaridan tashqari, xodimning xohishiga ko'ra, bevosita sudlarda ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Xodimning arizasini ko'rib chiqishni yakka tartibdagi nizo mehnat nizolari bo'yicha komissiyada ko'rib chiqilmaganligiga asoslangan holda rad etishga yo'l qo'yilmaydi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Mehnat kodeksi tahriri loyihasining 218-moddasiga ko'ra, agar hafta oxiri dam olish kuni ishlanmaydigan bayram kuniga to'g'ri kelsa, dam olish kuni bayramdan keyingi ish kuniga ko'chiriladi. Demak, agar Qonun loyihasi qabul qilinib kuchga kirsam, mehnat qonunchiligida belgilangan 9 ta bayramdan biri dam olish kuniga to'g'ri kelsa, dam olish kuni bayramdan keyingi ish kuniga ko'chiriladi[4].

Tashkilot rahbari, uning o'rinbosari va tashkilot bosh buxgalteriga ta'rif. tahrirdagi Mehnat kodeksi 485-moddasiga asosan ana shu shaxslarga aniq ta'rif berilmoqda.

1. Tashkilot rahbari – Mehnat kodeksiga, boshqa normativ-huquqiy hujjatlarga, tashkilotning ta'xis hujjatlariga, ichki hujjatlarga muvofiq mazkur tashkilotga rahbarlikni amalga oshiruvchi, shu jumladan uning yagona ijro etuvchi organi vazifalarini bajaruvchi jismoniy shaxsdir.

2. Tashkilot rahbarining o'rinbosari – rahbar yo'qligida uning vazifasini vaqtincha bajarib turish yoki lavozim vazifalari taqsimoti asosida ayrim masalalar bo'yicha rahbar vazifasini bajarish o'z xizmat vazifalari jumlasiga kiruvchi shaxsdir.

3. Tashkilot bosh buxgalteri:

- tashkilotda shtatdagi lavozimni egallab turgan;
- hisob siyosatini shakllantirish, buxgalteriya hisobini yuritish, to'liq va haqqoniy buxgalteriya, soliq va statistika hisobotlari o'z vaqtida taqdim etilishi uchun javob beruvchi;
- amalga oshirilayotgan xo'jalik operatsiyalarining qonunchilikka muvofiqligini, tashkilot mol-mulking harakati va majburiyatlari bajarilishi ustidan nazoratni ta'minlovchi shaxsdir.

Ijtimoiy ta'tilning mana bu turidagi farqni ko'ring[5].

1. Amaldagi Mehnat kodeksi 232-moddasi:

- 12 yoshga to'lmagan 2 va undan ortiq bolasi yoki 16 yoshga to'lmagan nogironligi bo'lgan bolasi bor ayollarga har yili 3 ish kunidan kam bo'lmagan muddat bilan haq to'lanadigan qo'shimcha ta'til beriladi.

2. Mehnat kodeksi 401-moddasi:

- 12 yoshga to'lmagan 2 va undan ortiq bolaning yoki 16 yoshga to'lmagan nogironligi bo'lgan bolaning ota-onasidan biriga (ota-ona o'rnini bosuvchi shaxsga) har yili davomiyliigi kamida 4 kalendar kun bo'lgan haq to'lanadigan qo'shimcha ta'til beriladi.

Mehnati kodeksi bo'yicha ishga qabul qilish haqidagi buyruqlarning mazmuni.

1. Ishga qabul qilish ish beruvchining buyrug‘i bilan rasmiylashtiriladi.
2. Buyruq chiqarish uchun xodim bilan tuzilgan mehnat shartnomasi asos bo‘ladi.
3. Ishga qabul qilish to‘g‘risidagi buyruqning mazmuni mehnat shartnomasining shartlariga muvofiq bo‘lishi kerak.
4. Buyruq xodimga ish haqiqatan boshlangan kundan e‘tiboran 3 kun ichida imzo qo‘ydirib e‘lon qilinadi.
5. Xodimning talabiga ko‘ra ish beruvchi unga mazkur buyruqning lozim darajada tasdiqlangan ko‘chirma nusxasini berishi shart.
6. Xodimning mehnat daftarchasiga mazkur buyruq asosida ishga qabul qilish to‘g‘risidagi yozuv qayd etilishi va xodim bu yozuv bilan 3 kun ichida tanishtirilishi kerak.
7. Ish beruvchi buyruq asosida ishga qabul qilish haqidagi ma‘lumotlarni “Yagona milliy mehnat tizimi” idoralararo dasturiy-apparat kompleksiga ham kiritadi.
(Mehnat kodeksi 127-moddasi).

Xulosa. Mehnat kodeksida mehnat erkinligi har kimning mehnat qilishga bo‘lgan o‘z qobiliyatlarini tasarruf etish, ularni qonun bilan taqiqlanmagan har qanday shaklda amalga oshirish, mashg‘ulot turini, kasbni va mutaxassislikni, ish joyini hamda mehnat sharoitlarini erkin tanlash huquqini anglatadi.

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INGLIZ TILIDA "MAISHIY TEXNIKA" TERMINOLOGIK GURUHINING SHAKLLANISHI.

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Annotatsiya: Ingliz tilidagi "maishiy texnika" terminologiyasiga mansub so'zlarning birinchi fiksatsiyasining xronologiyasi tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, zamonaviy tarixiy lug'atlarga ko'ra, o'rganilayotgan terminologiya XVI asrda paydo bo'lgan. Maxsus lug'atlarda bu davrda 3 ta leksemaning paydo bo'lishi qayd etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: fotoapparat, asbob, maishiy texnika, qurilma, tizim.

Shunday qilib, tahlil qilingan inglizcha so'zlarning birinchi qatori kettle (choynak) so'zi bo'lib, paydo bo'lish sanasi 1542 yil. Binobarin, ingliz tilida maxsus lug'atning o'rganilayotgan sohasining shakllanishi 16-asrda "suyuqlikni qaynatish yoki qizdirish uchun qurilma" ma'nosini anglatuvchi leksema bilan boshlanadi.

Hozirgi zamon nuqtai nazaridan, bu leksema umumiy atama bo'lmay, biroz keyinroq paydo bo'lgan asbob (apparat, asbob, moslama,) bosh atamasi bilan tobe munosabatda bo'ladi. Lug'atlar ushbu giperonimning paydo bo'lish sanasini 1597 yilda aniqlaydi.

Biroz vaqt o'tgach, maxsus lug'atning o'rganilayotgan sohasining asosiy nomlaridan biri – machine (mashina, mexanizm, qurilma) so'zi - 1549 yil.

Ko'rib chiqilayotgan terminologiyadagi eng qadimiy gipernim (1549) bo'lgan leksema mashinasi eng ko'p so'z yasovchi bog'lanishlarga ega: *answering machine, coffee machine, dishwashing machine, frying machine, icnitting-machine, sewing-machine, steam-machine va boshqalar.*

Sanab o'tilgan atamalarning (giponimlarning) paydo bo'lishi ikkita hodisadan dalolat beradi: birinchi hodisa fikrlash bilan bog'liq bo'lib, odamni uning mavjudligini yanada

qulayroq qiladigan ob'ektlarni yaratish imkoniyatlarini amalga oshirishga qodir ekanligini tavsiflaydi.

Ikkinchi hodisa giperonimning ajralmas qismi bo'lgan giponim chegaralarini aniqlashga urinish, aniqlovchi komponentni kiritish orqali tushuncha chegaralarini aniqlashtirish zarurati bilan bog'liq.

XVII asrda tarixiy lug'atlarga ko'ra o'rganilayotgan soha termini 5 ta leksema bilan to'ldirildi. Demak, leksema shakllarning ko'rinishi qayd qilinadi: apparatus (qurilma, asbob, apparat, mashina) - 1628, device (qurilma, moslama, apparat, mashina) - 1665, system (tizim) - 1683, coffee -mill (kofe tegirmoni) - kabi. 1691. Bu leksema shakllarning belgilanishi inson tomonidan yaratilgan mexanik buyumlar va asboblarni nomlash va tasniflash zarurligini bildiradi.

1673 yilda iron (dazmol) so'zining paydo bo'lishi qayd etilgan, bu ikkita hodisani ko'rsatadi: birinchisi, ob'ektning o'zi va uning nomini olish bilan bog'liq. Inson tafakkurining rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq ikkinchi hodisa insonning o'z hayotining qulayligini yaxshilash istagini ko'rsatadi.

18-asrda tahlil qilingan lug'atning yanada progressiv rivojlanishi qayd etilgan.

Shuni aytish kerakki, ko'plab tadqiqotchilar (S.V. Grinev, A.S. Grinev, E.A. Pankratova, A.V. Ponidelko, L.V. Shchekoldina va boshqalar) XVIII asr giper-giponimik munosabatlar bilan ajralib turadigan tizimli birikmalar tarkibiga nomutanosib leksemalar kiritilgan asr sifatida belgilandi.

18-asrda o'zlashtirilgan asbob-uskunalar (apparat, apparatus) - 1714) leksemasi giponim (uskunalar) ga aylanadi.

Xorijiy leksemalarning (ventilator (shamol parrak) - 1743 va washing machine (kir yuvish mashinasi) - 1780) ingliz tilida paydo bo'lishi ingliz hayotining yaxshilanishi nafaqat ularning o'z sa'y-harakatlari, balki chetdan keltirilgan qurilmalar yordamida ham sodir bo'lganligini ko'rsatadi. kundalik hayot sohasidagi madaniyatlararo aloqalarning natijasi ham texnik vositalarning o'zi, ham ularni bildiruvchi so'zlardir.

19-asrda tematik guruhlarga ko‘ra shakllangan leksemalar ko‘p. Tarixiy lug‘atlarda 47 ta leksemaning paydo bo‘lishi qayd etilgan.

Vaqt o‘tishi bilan o‘z shaklida quyidagi o‘zgarishlarga uchragan camera (kamera, fotoapparat) qo‘shma leksemasi paydo bo‘lishi - 1839-yil: camera (kamera, fotoapparat) - 1839, camera (kamera, fotoapparat) - 1840), "Kundalik hayotda ishlatiladigan asboblari va anjomlar" tematik guruhini boshlaydi.

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Approach to word formation in terms of derivation

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Annotation

Language is a great gift of nature, unique to man and humanity alone. This is a great gift of humanity is the most important means of communication of the society and serves the society. Language exists only in society, between groups of people, because through language people express their thoughts, exchange ideas, and talk. Language is a constantly changing, progressive phenomenon. The fate of the language is closely related to the fate of society. If there is no society, there is no language, and conversely, if there is no language, there is no development in society. Exchange of ideas is a constant and vital necessity for humanity.

Key words: *development, affixoids, derivation, Uzbek language, linguistics, word formation, affixes. Phenomenon, separate.*

The language was created by thousands of generations living in this society during the entire history of the society over the centuries, and serves the society and its members equally. The difference between language and social phenomena such as literature, art, and culture in general is that they look after the interests of a certain class, promote its ideology, and language serves the same for all people in society.

The development of the lexicon of the Uzbek language was enriched in several ways. In addition, new words were created from the internal resources of the Uzbek language, many words from the vocabulary of the Uzbek language underwent a semantic shift and began to express a new meaning. In addition, our language was enriched by learning new words from a foreign language. Dialect words and dialect words also contributed a lot to the Uzbek language. All the work done on learning the Uzbek language is aimed at one main goal, that is, for the development of the modern Uzbek literary language and for its development in all fields. For this purpose, Uzbek linguistics studies and solves problems in several areas. Among these problems, the field of word formation is also of great importance. In addition to word formation, Uzbek language grammar, phonetics, lexicology, phraseology, lexicography, dialectology, comparative linguistics, speech culture, history of the Uzbek language are also studied. In the first chapter of this research work, we will focus on the field of word formation.

One of the main factors in the development of the lexicon of the Uzbek language is the formation of words within the capabilities of one's own language. The creation of new and new words, their reflection of new meanings, has become of great importance in linguistics. Because of this, word formation is studied as a separate department in linguistics.

Word formation is one of the independent branches of linguistics, which studies the formation of new words, methods of word formation, and phenomena related to word formation. As in the development of any language, there are changes in its lexicon, grammatical structure and other areas, in the formation of words there are various changes over the years. For example, word-formation methods may be active or inactive, or words that were historically made-up words may not be made-up words today.

The main way of word formation is affixation, because the task of word formation is to create a new lexical unit. «The words and lexicon of every language are always in motion, as a result of which its content undergoes various changes, some words become old and fall out of active use, their use is limited, and they gradually fall out of use. , new words appear, which fill and enrich the lexicon».

The article is devoted to the problem of affixation in modern European languages. Under the term affixoid, we understand word-forming elements that are characteristic of both affixes and word stems. The main feature that usually belongs to affixes is productivity. Due to this feature, affixoids help to develop new semantic and grammatical categories. As affixes, affixoids can represent a wide word-forming category (person, object, sign, location), have high productivity, can perform a task. Therefore, the object of research is lexical units of intermediate status, that is, affix signs and word stems. are those who have The purpose of the study is to prove the existence of word-forming elements with intermediate status in English and their specific characteristics. In this scientific work, affixoids, which mean the word-formative meaning of the intermediate state with both affix and root characters, are analyzed.

Recently, compounding has become not only the main method of creating new words, but also a very important and effective source of new derivative elements. This phenomenon can be explained by the fact that the word formation of modern languages is characterized by the tendency to form new compound words by analogy according to patterns already

existing in language systems. In addition, according to some scientists, the formation of words by analogy is leading in the creation of terms. So, in modern languages, one can observe the tendency to economize language actions: instead of phrases and phrases, we use compound words. It is built according to models that are distinguished by a high level of productivity in languages. New words are formed not on the basis of a unit of syntactic level in the language, but by adding a recurring component that has some semantic meaning. Often in such cases, elements in the preceding position and elements in the following position develop the functions of affixes (for example, classifying and generalizing). These elements can be called affixoids (similar to affixes). The large number of such units determines the relevance of this work and its purpose - to reveal the scope of this term and develop possible principles of classification.

The relevance of the work can be explained by the existence of the problem, and affixoidation has not been analyzed in the linguistic literature. This means that it is important to define the scope of the term “affixoid”, to define as clearly as possible the principles of classification and typology. Another important question is related to possible semantic changes if we compare independent root morphemes and constituents of compound words. The problem of affixoids and affixoidization is worth discussing and analyzing as a specific linguistic process, because modern European languages are characterized by a large number of such word-forming elements. Common everyday words are directly included in the material of the scientific work. These lexical units are analyzed using distributional analysis, word formation analysis, and analysis of available language resources.

For many years, it has been a rule of generative morphology that affixes are chosen according to the class of their base. For example, using the familiar notation, the affixes -er and -ize in English show the feature of selection. That is, -er is added to verbs and nouns and forms a noun; -ize is added to nouns and adjectives to form verbs. Although there has been debate over aspects of selection, such as whether affixes are always selected for a single category of base, a concept first proposed by Aronoff (1976) as the unitary base hypothesis, or whether they can select multiple categories as they have proposed! Liberda (1980) - the general concept of c-selection has not been seriously challenged.

However, a number of recent theories of word formation first suggested that roots do not have a specific syntactic category, first suggested in Chomsky's 1970 article Reflections on Nominalization. Proponents of this concept argue that roots are systematically categorized by syntactic or morphological functional category because they are c-order. The syntactic approach is a central tenet of Distributed Morphology (Embick and Noyer, in press; Halle and Marantz, 1993; Harley and Noyer, 1999; Marantz, 1997) and Borer's exoskeletal approach to word formation (2003); a morphological approach is taken in DiSciullo's Asymmetric Morphology (2005). Such theories pose at least one obvious challenge to the notion of c-selection: if roots have no category, then affixes cannot select particular categories of roots.

The idea that roots are inherently uncategorical is provocative, and for languages like English where conversion is common, it has intuitive appeal. Nevertheless, it is argued that it can only be clearly categorized by semantic or morphosyntactic features within a theory that provides a clear alternative to syntactic categories, such as the theory developed in Lieber (2004). This argument is based on issues of selection: one way or another, a theory of word-formation must recognize and account for the tendency to select which affixes attach to which bases.

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The role of public finance in social protection

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Annotatsiya. This article describes the government by the social protection needs of the population of protection to the complexity of financial reforms analysis of the studied was hug with in conjunction public finance role analysis has been.

Keywords: population, social protection, finance, government, pension, social assistance.

To enter. The constitution of the republic of uzbekistan of social policy and other legal documents with a set of social rights and guarantees of citizens poured the implementation of the priority directions of activities aimed at you.

In the country in 2007. "social protection" year of social protection to be declared, to provide the practical expression of state policy is aimed at improving the level of living.

The main part.

"Social protection" year of the state program focuses on social protection provisions , I set the priority direction to perform the following tasks.

- different categories of vulnerable layers of the population, first and foremost alone senior citizens, persons with disabilities, children who have reached puberty supporter lost to the display at the rate of maqbullashtirish norms and social support;

the homes of older and persons with disabilities, children, married and suffering from diseases for children in riniternatlarni, war veterans and labor for the treatment ofpros - term regulatory agencies to provide the spending of the amount of material costs maqbullashtirishbrowsing;

- Children under the age of 2 to the mother of many children and families to the neighborhood committee members have material and social help rendered by the revision of their amount;

- "Mercy" homes and special schools-boarding schools of the world material-technical base mustaxhamlash toe, wish more attention to enhancing the rest of the children were the ones, "you are not alone" to ensure the practical implementation of the humanitarian life motto;
- social protection of vulnerable layers of the population to boost the system vulnerable families, of pearron clear and effective social and the elderly to help increase it to show their needs, and ensuring more complete satisfaction, and to show them material assistance and moral support, social ko'llab-kuvvatlash measures apply to enhancing the role of communities in increasing;
- 2. "Mercy", "Generously" and "Compassion" homes of the staff's social service system and appropriate valuation mexanigi stimulating work in those nizmini improvement;
- eitherto protect the vital interests of shlar, and their ability and potential to create the conditions to young families to independent living in them moral and material incentives steps the selfantirish ko'llab way to support young families to give preferential loans.

1-picture. **The legal basis of social policy reform**

The country First by the president on 19 December, adopted in 2007, "and the further improvement of the system of social protection of the population to which measures related

to strengthening to'g'i on"the vital importance of a decree of the population in need of protection layers ko'llab ijti-kuvvatlash is a continuation of reforms aimed at. This decree of the population, further strengthening of social protection for poor families through the necessary material assistance ko'llab-kuvvatlash, providing the work of the staff of the social service system and stimulating the improvement of the payment mechanism, the institutions of social protection of the population of material-technical base aimed at strengthening.

1-table

Social policy, the main yo'of nalisth

In the field of production:	in the field of Consumption	in the field of social protection:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •the employment of already highjasi to achieve •mass customization and ravishtasarrufidan event production at statelabor oshirilayogganda out of the world to comply with the interests of the community; •work previously installed aloqalirini storage; •small business and private entrepreneurshipfor the development of the social conditions that create it. •Income distribution and re - distribution in the field: •salaries, pensions, allowances, scholarships, specify the minimum amount of yalar; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •the protection of the domestic consumer market; •the delivery of consumer goodsto stimulate; •the free exchange of goods conditions create •basic consumer goods of the sharp decline in the level of production avoided; •high-calorie food iste' beef products questions of the content ofemergency; •the consumption of social services alreadyput in the way of the sharp decline of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dahldor to the family character of the benefits ofthe pros; • the targeted population on the basis of social protection; • families nafaqalar arranged by neighborhood; • for social protection of the population of the state with financial resources in number, sponsored, this charitable organizationfunds attract settings.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • income and vulnerable citizens in favor of the distribution of 	<p>jasisee that it was possible measures.</p>	
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Social protection of the population using umumjamyat work out how to participate in the activity, despite of the population made to improve the level of living of certain segments carried.

Currently in the republic of social assistance in the home, the types indicated:

1. Children, families benefits: - spend on pregnancy and childbirth;
 - child allowances at once give birth; - care allowances for children up to the age of 2 years; - there are benefits to the families of the minor children.
2. Social benefits: - congenital to persons with disabilities persons with disabilities and other categories; - no to nursing work experience; - to the families who lost supporter.
3. The storage of social security institutions: - the homes of the elderly and persons with disabilities; - orphan homes - morbid for children are boarding.
4. Various benefits: - free and cost reduction in the vehicle and give the wheelchair; - sanatorium-resort provide you with a ticket; - prosthetics; - concerning payment for public utility services and taxation benefits.
5. Poverty benefits: - Ijtimoiy the main source of funding assistance program is in addition to funds from the state budget and the budget.

2-table

Social sector expenditure composition

Social service sector,	<i>Social protection,</i>	Social sug'rtasi
Education	16 under the age of children who would to families benefits	Retirement sug'rtasi
Culture	who do not work in mother 2 child under the age of care for tulanadigan benefits	Unemployment on sug'rtasi

Science	Working mother of 2 child under the age of care for tulanadigan spend	Cocktail to pass the ability yuq,the slugs on sug'rta
Sog'social storage	Less equipped to the families of material assistance	Medical sug'rta
Physical education	Chernobil of xalokat oqibatlarini eliminating the costs	
of social security	Scholarship	
Employment service,	Unemployment benefits	

The state budget funds hjesus: - children, families benefits; - feed the elders and persons with disabilities and the services uyidagilar show; - to teach disabled people to work, to employment, to put the prosthesis; - Chernobil' aes participate in the disaster in, to persons with disabilities are given financial assistance.

Allowances for children, the financing of the state budget, at the expense of the form of ownership, as well as from in spite of enterprises, institutions and organizations of the templeat the expense of lag'lari is also carried out.

Currently, the neighborhood social support system are carried out through funding from the budget of the following main types: kbenefits to families at issued, until the child reached the age of two monthly benefits to people of your care, vn oya the families of children who reachedafaqa, orphans and children of parents of children qarovisiz supply in a complete state of rest home and spend money on clothes, shoes and benefits to purchase supplies.

Less of allowances to the families who supported her monthly financial assistance to the family of 3 (three) appointed for a period of months and will be paid. Less of allowances to the families who supported funds from the national budget, local (regional, city and district) budget and extra-budgetary funds of the various sources (public and charitable funds, management companies and funds of citizens and others voluntary donation) are

financed at the expense of. Rural funds, or the citizens of the neighborhood or self-government bodies is held to the relevant institutions of the savings bank and does not take special schyot.

The amount of financial assistance the most current monthly wage to the amount of from 1.5 to 3 times the minimum wage is determined. Expiry of the term of payment of financial assistance, the help rendered permanent residence cases the change in the material condition of the family, or when fill material changes from stopped to help.

The mother until the child reached the age of two who do not work to your care to the people of monthly benefits at the expense of local budget funds is carried out. They cost the state budget economic classification "250" is "5" paragraph of the "03" cost type "4" object "25" reflected on the small object.

Citizens' self-governance bodies appointed by the following:

- mothers who do not work or persons who replace them (usually the father, the son, the borrower, make, guardians or other relatives);
- separated from the production in the case of higher and secondary professional educational institutions at secondary paid-contract basis or to the person who read mothers who replace them;
- engaged in entrepreneurial activities without forming a legal entity to the mother (mother to the person who replace), as well as activity without forming a legal entity which is carried out to the members of the peasant farms.

The benefits of child care every month, and the number of children who receive care from the labor of persons who benefits from this experience, regardless of the applicable minimum wage is 200% of the amount I paid.

A working mother of two young children to care filled with monthly benefits on the budget in organizations (institutions) running (allow for reading separated from the production, and thus paid-up contract on the basis of enrollment is not included, the service passing) of the mother (mother substituting the person) at the expense of the budget is carried out. These costs are the costs of the state budget economic classification of expenses type "03" account "4" analytical accounting "20" is displayed. Regardless of the form of

ownership in the other directory (in the organization) working mothers (mother substituting persons) for this directory (organization) is carried out at their own expense.

The age of two the child care allowances for the care of the mother to two children reached the age of kilinayotgan when specialized institutions to the children (infants to house) full in the state to supply the children died, the family, together with the children from the territory of the republic of uzbekistan for permanent residence in the case of stopped going out.

Of the republic of uzbekistan 's first President “children, families and support the further strengthening of the state on 10 December 1996 in the up-dated 1657 and “social protection of the population in need of support focused on enhancing the layers clearly in a way” January 25, 2002 in the up-3107-dated in accordance with the decree are children under the age of 16, as well as in secondary schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges of education in the bearing of benefits to families with children from the age of 16 berlin is under the age of 18.

N to families with minor children need to take these benefits afaqa, birth, and childhood homiylikka (guardian) be taken under the age of 16 (“in secondary schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges of education in the bearing under the age of 18 from the age of 16”) is given to families with children.

Twenties who reached the children of the families benefits:

- a children of the family to - most less monthly work fee of 50% of i in the amount of;
- two children, families for - 100 % i amount;
- three children, families for I - 140 % i amount;
- four and her many children, families for - 175 % i amount is determined.

With disabilities, children, and families; parents both also is, of children, the rearing with while relatives involved families; children of parents one or both also disabled , who is the family; his parents, one or both are either unemployed are, labor in exchange for work looking for as your account's standing of a family, the benefits of getting a privilege to the right has.

Twenties who reached the children of the families benefits , republic of the budget and local budgets, funds of the budget, except the source of funds is funded by.

In the republic, full - state supply orphans children and parents qarovisiz the remaining children money, benefits and clothes-home, shoes and supplies to buy to get to the benefits, as well as in transport walking cards with will be provided.

Full state supply orphans children and parents qarovisiz the remaining of children and social protection to make in order to them all kinds of comprehensive school and graduated from university when out and to work joylashayotganda clothing-general, shoes and supplies to buy to get to the benefits of doing most less monthly work fee of 100 times the minimum wage up to the amount of, most are less monthly to work to pay the amount of 5 times the minimum wage to the amount of money the benefits of also is given.

Benefits of educational institutions graduates of educational institutions graduates to work joylashayotganida a time is given. You in this institution trained providers from 9th grade to graduation, academic, school , or vocational college, 11-class graduates, higher education institutions have to read and enter, the graduates of each of two of the benefits of this educational institution to study completing after the same institution gets. Paid benefits and money benefits for the costs of the amount they tarbiyalanayotgan education institutions or study to continue , which was academic lyceums and professional colleges of the costs estimates in budget expenditures economic classification on 03-4-90 article "Home to the farm and other transfert the" substance on to reflect is held.

Mercy homes and schools-boarding schools in tarbiyalanayotgan, secondary schools, academic school or vocational college in reading the full state supply orphans children and parents qarovisiz the remaining children who read education establishments, and live from the place 3 from miles more than the distance located in is, they public transport and pupils for transport in preferential walk of cards in circulation in the city and population in point of preferential transport in walk cards or transport in preferential walk to the right , allowing other types of cards is given.

Conclusion. The population of a job with to provide its revenue raising is the most important factor is. Do this to place regional "Employment" programs, work out, out should be done. For this purpose the employment assistance fund from the account the funds should be allocated and provided the following recipe should fall:

- young people, women, on the employment of special events invalidlarni implementation;
- improve the quality of labor force, kasbkorlikka of the population who are busy with work training, retraining and improvement of the training system;
- men self-employed small business and private entrepreneurship development.
- targeted social protection of the population of the character, increasing the level of living of the poor and vulnerable most of the population social protection measures to enhance the importance of the layer, and the implementation of measures on social protection of the population tabaqalashgan address and the further strengthening of approach, to provide the necessary financial assistance to families.

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Socio-economic development the role of the sector of operation for small business

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Abstract. In this article, the influence of the sectors on small business development, rolan in its social-economic development and clonal statistical data are studied.

Keywords: small business, entrepreneurship, Investments, competition, socio-economic development.

To enter. The development of small and private business in the republic before the beginning of reforms in the domestic market with products and services of filling first and foremost it was made to look as the solution of the problem. And it is noteworthy to say today, small business full of goals and objectives established before their structures are performing. Small business and private structures they are building new business areas themselves without large financial resources, a shortage of goods, the possibility of reduction in the domestic market, the competitive environment and agriculture an important role in the decision they take has an absolute advantage find some of the territorial unit in the republic, which represented the main source of local budget revenues with his expected results. This with along get who go to many analysis according to yet up to the national economy and its territorial unit in small business development for the available potential in practice full their expression find not.

Small business in today's day in the development of this sector of the regions and economic sectors of development, great attention is paid. Because, mohiyatan, a small business first and foremost local consumer satisfaction and territorial unit of the economic potential of effective use to, this it the regions of development of the issue on the order puts. Same as the aspect also small business and private entrepreneurship in the regions at the level of studies to issue an actual character acquires.

The main part.

Mohiyatan small business entrepreneurial and business skills of the population, the development of economic activity, high respects, and the same means that have the potential to irritability of the population are adapted to boosts the level of market conditions. Small business of a society like this of socio-economic, and political relations in the system of the position, especially in the context of the transition period for developing countries plays an important role. Of this republic 's first president, in 2006 the country's socio-economic development of deepening economic reforms in priority areas dedicated in 2007 to the cabinet of ministers “to move from the path of renewal and sustainable development more consistent, abundant living conditions for the people we create basic task” based on deep analysis of mutual small business named on the report given showing three lived in harmony:

- the necessary goods in the internal market (services) and fill with the improvement of the structural basis of the economy in the same manner, increase the level of employment and income of the population;

- mobility, less capital spending in exchange for the organization of production, modernization, expansion of the product range able to get the feature, according to the market through the same power and flexibility to quickly change and growing competition from the aspect of improving quality at the same time as an active participant in the cultivation of embodied relations;

- small business and private entrepreneurship in the developing countries, the most active part of the population – the middle class, they bring the functions in the formation of proprietors of the layer can be based on the example[1].

Given the president by showing these three featured role in the development of small business in the country, according to the aspect in the economic evaluation and future effect not remain confined only expected of him should. Accordingly, each secured in the field of small business as a result of his social life tasks, instead of at the same time also economic, social and political also plays a role.

Exactly the same quality, according to the small business structures related to the development of wide-ranging economic reforms are recognized as priority factor. As a

result, today the role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the national economy of the structures has increased significantly. Thus, in the years of independence in uzbekistan following the development of small business through a number of practical outcomes vividly structures can be expressed as:

Small business in gdp, the share of the increase in them by therefore, the reforms carried out in terms of increasing the size of the products is the result. By the way, the recent years (2010 – 2020)at a small business in gdp, the share 25,5 percent to handle increased in the year 2020 53,9 percent up made (1st picture).

1-picture

Small business and private entrepreneurship in the structure dynamic analysis of the share of the gross domestic product of the country, in percent[2]

Because in the next years the share of industrial production growing at a fast pace in the national economy in conditions of the small business network small business in uzbekistan is exactly in the structure of the industry did not take a position on the level of potential available in the sector. About this target of the president of the country induced transition according to the following review: “another issue that requires particular attention in our country at the present time the small business and private entrepreneurship, mainly in trade and services in the field of communications, are found more on the development of agricultural products processing.

But, at the same time, industry in the field of modern high technology, which require the organization of production networks, innovation and nanotexnologiya of pharmacology

and pharmaceutical, information and communications, biotechnology, the use of a type in the field of alternative energy, in short words, small business and private entrepreneurship, the development of advanced science based on the achievements of the way to wide open,”we need to[3].

1 table.

Small business and private entrepreneurship on the territory included in the volume of investments into the main capital of the share, in percent[2]

Country	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
O‘of uzbekistan uzbekistan , the republic of	up to 28.5	31,9	's 35.3	32,7	35,4	40,3	40,9	38,1	38	47
Qoraqalpog‘iston republic of the	33	26,7	53,9	17,9	12,3	12,2	17,4	36	28,4	Became 32.1
at andizhan	45	43,9	41	47,2	52,1	58	60,9	63,9	57,7	67,3
Bukhara	12.8 Percent	18,3	16,7	19,4	21	24,9	17,7	11.6	28,1	54,4
Dzhizak	50,1	47,7	47,6	38,9	44	Was 62.9	To 60.8	60,1	45,1	69,2
Kashkadarya	23,3	18	15,1	14,1	Warp 13.9	19	21,4	14,4	12,6	29,7
Navoi	12,7	22,6	23	TI 24.8	27	And 33.2	22,2	26	14,3	19,3
Namangan	40,7	Extended To 54.2	55,5	51,9	39,7	Surged 49.6	55,7	50,5	37,3	Extended To 54.2
Samarkand	42,7	49,7	50,8	48,2	57,5	65,7	65,2	65,3	59,8	62,3
Surkhandarya	31,8	Psalm 33,6	40,9	37,7	45,1	54,6	56,3	38,6	Has A 39,6	Was 74.7
Syrdarya	31	25,6	29,9	29,1	25,7	37,4	44,9	48,5	extended to 54.2	61,2
Tashkent	25,9	A 28.2	38,7	29,2	36,2	36,8	42,4	45,8	39,5	33,9
Farg‘mother	37,5	40,4	41,1	33,8	42,3	57,9	55,3	55,2	equals to 54,3	60,6

Architecture	55,5	47,4	49,5	32,9	45,8	59,8	64,6	57,5	clim bed fro m 48.9	65
Tashkent city.	32,8	36,1	38,3	49,2	56,4	58,2	51,8	52,2	up to 53.6	46,6

Small business and private entrepreneurship of the activities of the statistical analysis of the results, we see that this area is uneven investment in the region separates the network incisions can. Total capital investment in year 2019 included in our republic, the major KBXTning if the share was 47%, while on the territory of the republic of karakalpakstan to the lower region of the republic of the figure (it became 32.1), Kashkadarya(29,7), Navoi (19,3), Tashkent (33,9), tashkent (46,6) percent. The remaining regions, while the republic ko‘from rsatkich large that we can(1 table).

Kinside business and private entrepreneurship in the structure of the employment relationship allows the analysis of produced another important conclusion, that is, the structure in the past years the growth in the number of those who are employed in general compared to the number of employed in the economy is greater than the growth rate of 4.8 times. That is, those who are employed in other areas of earlier social production of their business a substantial portion of small business and private entrepreneurship structures also changed. This in turn represents the structural changes that will take place in the economy significantly.

Respublika small and private businesses in the area of the fountains of the gross domestic product contributing to the production of that we have observed in the analysis of the annual growth, regional aspects of the development of this sector in the country to afford variations is removed. These variations in the regions of the country and currently specializes in the development of the specialization of small business network in the network vary from each other in the level of efficiency is caused by. Consequently, Navoi, navoi region, mainly in industrial production specialization fountains network mining, chemical, oil and gas sectors like the basis for competence in the processing industry, as well as the number and the density of the population in this region is relatively low for other regions, they are natural conditions of the region and the ratio of employment to the network in the

production of gross regional product of this contribution remains at low level, some of the small businesses.

The role of small business in the social life of the country being large full scale marketing with its current growth rate in relation to the level of the potential available acquires imbalance. This can be explained by the following circumstances.

Bugungi days rendered one of the main problems in small business creation and development – small business jabhadagi the number of entities that work in the jobs they've created, pay attention to the growth of production volume, as well as the benefits towards them, powerful qolinayotganligidir limited to the improvement of the protection system. In this regard hobby at the same time change the quality to achieve a task.

In this place it's simple primary processing of raw materials, high-tech production has been about the need to transition to the production says," were noted[1].

The practical execution of the task that was put by the president of the country in many ways the region, local and network small business development approach in the economy to rethink radically the program's exit, makes improvements requires. We, now being developed in the program for the development of regional and local small businesses on small business network tashkillanishi network and reduction of regional disparities; economic and legal economy in the formation of skills of running a business; small business sector and the size of the investment that will be attracted to their composition, source solutions, a description of the current technology in their enterprises, and the effectiveness on local and regional level; the program during the duration of the study and regulation of their activities to the control condition, the number of complaints and applications, and content analysis; the condition of the offenders has been put by way of small businesses, the organization of small businesses, be discontinued, re-registration, and the causes of their condition temporary stop of activity should be also taken into account. Approach to the improvement of the software: a) to strengthen the legal system of running the farm; b) increase the level of guaranteeing the freedom of the activities of business organizations; v) investment to support the participation of small business in the market; g) and small business

in all kinds of business entities with the responsibility to commit their views to the formation of economic activity creates the opportunity.

At the same time, the network only share the small business industry in the next five years steady, consistent grew at a pace that can be observed.

Of course, the core sectors of industrial production – mining qazlov, metal processing, machine building, oil-chemical production mainly tend to be major in some developed countries, includingapon according to the practice, and effectiveness of the activities of many of these large producers continuous cooperation with aspects of their small business depends on. Accordingly, in this sector of the industry, component parts, yarimfabrikat, and production of secondary products, the delivery aspects such as small business entities to organize resources in industrial production and the activities of small business development in the area of cooperation with them creates a wide opportunity. In this regard, the country that first adopted in 2006 by the president on the development of the work from home model, the function of specific orders are performing.

Also at the complex at the same time, traditional areas of small business development in today's agricultural production – farms and small farms should continue to improve the activities of consistent work. This is first and foremost, qualitatively at small business development network development, as well as fulfilling some kind of farms in rural areas, social and personal services the company previously come now the responsibility of local government entities associated with the passage of time without the need for additional financial resources to meet the needs of the local budget can be expressed by.

But still, this have been recorded in the relevant territorial unit as and does not express the content of the small business network

- oqsayotganligi of the activities of major industrial development agencies (this in turn, first and foremost the sharp decline in their share in the gross regional product in exchange for going to be, as well as specific major economic entities in the territory of “pole” and have the same potential to play the role of negative influence caused by the decrease of the prosperity of small business);

- some who are unable to achieve a positive and significant structural shift in the industry in the union has the advantage of regional and local agricultural production;
- traditional transitional economy countries who have extensive track direction, that is, small business services, trade and the high share of agriculture sector in uzbekistan as for the cases in the country that is typical regional and regional small business development network is recognized as allowing the development of a set of variations from the aspect factor.

Islam is the 19th anniversary of the constitution of the republic on 6 December 2010 qilinganligining own part in the celebrations of the year in 2011 “the year of small business and private entrepreneurship” and the state program for accepted from dwell about the issues that this should take place on the following priorities and the focus of particular attention:

- the revision of the regulatory framework in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship, improvement;
- create a more favourable environment for small business and private entrepreneurship;
- for small business in the field of tax and other payments, as well as create convenience and light;
- small businesses and technological modernization of production to give further improvement of the system update for the medium and long term loans;
- activation of small business entities involved in the field of foreign economic activity;
- industry in the field of modern high technology, which require the organization of production networks, innovation and nanotexnologiya of pharmacology and pharmaceutical, information and communications, biotechnology, the use of a type in the field of alternative energy, in short words, advanced science based on the achievements of small business and private entrepreneurship development give way to wide open.[3]

We, as reflected in the life of this task and in this regard the organization of regional and local authorities of these government entities and small business development is largely associated with the increase active in the area of clearly defined functions plays an important role.

Conclusion. Liberalization of the economy of the process of the enhancement of the regions of the economy development in the area of a number of important task solution of the resolution will find out - comes. Chunonchi, the tasks can maintain the rule of

- the region 's economic independence and strengthen;
- state budget removable dotatsiya by which is covered local budget was a shortage there is the inside from potential using without fill;
- the region and thus increase the income level of the population to raise the level of living of the population;
- the employment level of the population, the increase of business;
- explain faster and deeper to find a resolution in the region of market relations;
- inside the region the territory of the local market and increase export capacity and resources, such as enriched at the expense of others appears.

Of course, the main responsibility in this regard the contribution made without denying the importance of the structure of the major production and fall on the shoulders of small and private business in many ways it should be noted a special place to be.

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The human factor is the significance

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Abstract. This article examines the essence of the human factor, its legal foundation, and its economic implications.

Key words: human factor, human capital, organization, labor resources, working power.

To enter. Hayotimizda listed'y giving cardinal o'zgarib one of the market iqtisodiyotining form. Of our republic the market iqtisodiyotiga o'teeth, most primarily iqtisodiy and social taraqqiyotni ta'minlash the units oftheozone is. These functions hal the for the country o'zini's rich natural resources, mineral source from hamda science-technical and human resources effective for use as necessary. After all, society most higher wealth toe'present on theq eternal theadriyatlarni, qudratli salohiyat the o'zida is accumulating. This salohiyat of occurrence ndqarib to our society's development and taraqqiy much of the development of very powerful factor is toe'become service of thewill ilar. Iupon ns salohiyat of the most active, most bunyodkor factor to toe'become , she of the country, islamhhorses and cardinal o'zgarib review either'lida unceasing progress that go to the units'minlash gives. In the republic iqtisodiy islamhof horses hozirgi in the period of work stqto the arib factors oqiloni the use of the problem e'tibor strengthen go totheat. Such factors as theator of in person incarnate brought to qobiliyatlardan use sohasi in research of these states to theqiqhorse of work ahamiyatlidir. The topic of the relevance of work thqarib of the first of the toe'present in the firm, the human from om oqiloni for the use required from come thqadi.

The main part.

Of the organization (firm corporation) is interested in the academy oftheatga to the ambassador receives'jalik in the process mehnat market working power to buy getting not,

but the organization's o'zida it iste'cost qilish in the process of hat show up toe'ladi. The organization of interest sale is derived from the working of the power of the desired quality and the structural ko'to rsatkich "treatment" to give, him korporativ ruh and organizational culture "qo'tumor" ha hat the garden'liq. This work stqto arib homethearib of the new trend from guvohmore gives.

Work stqarib in man (person) of the factor units'riflash for "working strength", "mehnat resources", "person", "servant", "work", such as the concepts are used.

Working power – material wealth and services to the production thqarib, the complexity man's physical and aqliy qobiliyatlarining is set.

Mehnat process to'g'rida ' from-to'g'settings, theara than it potential o'lchov unit as show up toe'ladi, this with along with mehnat – this activity ko'in rsat get, business ko'rsatayotgan working power.

Usually ithetisodiy in science working power as mehnat layaptiqatli the understanding, mehnat based on the man's maqa sad activity lies in.

Working power – this brand. The academyqat homeqa type of goods from farq,li in o'a worthy specific quality ko'to rsatkich able toe'ladi.

It's flexible toe'become, o'z properties quickly o'zgarib to tryingobiliyatiga have and the same on the basis of demand and offer of fields'yukturasiga active ta'secret ko'in rsat gets. Naturally, her a person mehnat in the market demand qilinadigan o'a worthy distinctive brand features a range has. Ayrimlarda it wide toe'lsa , hometo themany years ago in it is narrow. This while in person are knowledge, ustomonlik, experience and hometo themany years ago, ya'to the general words in the person's experience hamda his updates qabul qwith to get tryingobiliyatiga to'g'rida ' from-to'g'settings in the garden'liq toe'become qgets.

Mehnat resources as ahhigh all social active qthe name is understood to be. Such resources chief of thearib from maqsad – ahof taking the social activation of either'li with the family, personal, cultural, ecological , and iqtisodiy problems hal qtwisted. Mehnat in the process of human resources of great thename of those involved in theset. Mehnat sohasi

in the main e'tibor o'smir to, house to the mistress, nafaqaxo'rlar, disabilities, qaratiladi, qo'shimcha o'rindoshlik based on and in parallel on the basis of a work rag'batlantirish.

Mehnat resources to mehnat at the age of toe'present ahhigh qatl me enter, from them I and II guruh of disabled ththebee and nafa, theaxo'rlar of haqiqan israelite running qname theo'shib is. Yuqin ori qan audit , those who are small, e'tibor to loyithe toe'I lmas categories toe'in lsa, they each other with intertwined garden'liqis. Mehnat layaptiqatli toe'lmas without it I done increase can not, mehnat layaptiqlet atli while the academyqat mehnat in the process show up toe'ladi.

Mehnat resources – this is the whole of society mehnat toe'present layaptiqati toe'become, the academyqat its a with thename of (the house of the mistress, students and generalof theof many years ago mehnat toe'present layaptiqati) in society, work stqin arib is not used.

“Workers power” and “mehnat resources” man of material wealth and services to the production thqto arib for mo'ljallab the physical and aqliy qobiliyatleri association toe'become, they o'z before personal maqsad qo'ya can't, qanday is to request (by ehtiyojga) having toe'lmas were. Homeof theacha a qtrailthework with busy or creative activity with shug'ullana can't.

O'his zini tom ma'nosi with they plan receives ambassador'jalik doing sohof many years ago in the context of state institutions placed, taqcable, theI taqcable material and technical basis, creating for, iqtisodiy salohiyat of continuous boosts go to, the team is the property and national income increase to the service of thebirths.

An 80-year to the end of come iqtisodiyotda mehnat resources “shortage” lekarzemq ko'rinib when it started, mehnatkashlarga work stqarib to be a factor as in the approach will start.

Man work stqarib complexity o'rni the new thought theilish to 80-years o'in central iqtisodiy in the literature, “human factor” and “mehnat potential” the concepts of equal work started. It usually human factor concept, man iqtisodiyotga toe'did it big one'mystery to help maintain the expression of e'tibor qaratildi. This live mehnat from sufficient level of

unused new social hpenis far more suited was. “Human factor” , the concept of “working strength” and “mehnat resources” to the concept in relation wideq and chuqurrathe content o’zida hugs. “Factor” (“Factor”) , the concept of lug’in atlar any thing harakatlantiruvchi power as thearal is, ya’select “resource” concept contrary to that in her qanday thing, this hpenis in man's active (active) the role represents. Ko’pgina scientists (R. Laykert, Meskon m. h. and homein theit was many years ago), that's opinion , human capital, financial capital compared to qimmatliroq, this is the reason for hat the human resources of the whole society or alahida a firm in the development of alahida ahamiyat professional is. Thus, the human factor to the’g’rising is not, but “human resources” haqida idea yuritilmoqat.

Hired workers o’z mehnat hayo unhappy that grew in thehouse of the facts ko’rsat is: personnel qo’nim to solve, to work not come and afternoon thetake increased and homein theit was many years ago. All the while, o’z turn mehnat efficiency and its quality ko’to rsatkich negative ta’secret theof ilar and the servants of the creative o’sish to tryingthe arshi qwill ilar. Men association mehnat resources as qarash them technical, raw materials, energy and generalqmany years ago, ya’see work stqarib of material factors with balanced means. Such approach men receives the ambassador’jalik the process of conscious sub’yek as not, but chiefthearuv weather’yek's as thearal is. Iqtisodiy in science, “work”, ‘mehnatkash’, or “general - an individual who” o’to rni o’zini's all hayo ehtiyojlari with the living man to theo’yilma not unless human factors, chiefof thearib of a complex system haqida 's hat toe’lish will can not.

Work stqto arrib, iqtisodiy research and the society of human factor what is it? This question is general and lekarzemthe answer either’q. Akademik i. t. Zaslovskayaning opinion, the human factor of – “this her the same pog’mother in the class, theatl shops and guruhs joint harakat either’of nalish toe’become, their joint hof arakat and activities of the society of the efficiency with the development , including’minlash will”.

Homeof theacha qtwisted words, the human factor the human ko’pgina o’lchov in the open will: mehnatkash, fuq, among, the family head of’i, ko’p qirr with sensations and thoughts toe’present in human as.

Human factors of a person's personal characteristics of the set occurrence thqwork as qarash should. This while her mehnat in the process in the activity show up toe'ladi. This concept of man and of the work of stqto arib in the process hal qiluvchi role ko'rsat and gives.

Human factor – that the firm and in the organization shared activity ko'to rsat for who people are. Structural jihatdan while this is the first place in the person, the working guruh, mehnat team.

Human factor – this is the academy oftheatga to working in a team is not, but society hayo team sub'the yek toe'become o'zida society, the development of ta'minlash that social, demographic, iqtisodiy and political, the content represents.

Such an approach to society, the development of the people of social development for the necessary muhdog create as theto arash out comes. The man in his hayo ehtiyojlari with society, the development of equal to huquqli and insightful qatnashchisi as recognized olininshi, again his creative activity - toe'present ehtiyojini, information, homeqaruvdagi part and a homein theit was many years ago, the hat the first o'herring stqarib qo'yadi.

“Mehnat resources” and “human factor” the concept of her the same ingredients in them o'to rga for different approaches and methods require that qwill ilar. Ma'lum a institution, soha and the organisation of mehnat resources ko'pinch , the number of and location, sohaviy, professional and specialty ko'of rsatkich with ta'riflanadi. Work stqarib of the human factor in this ko'rsatkich from tashthebee mehnat toe'present e'tibor, initiative, entrepreneurship, thetrailof thework, ehtiyojlar, qadriyatlar, her the same conditions o'zini to keep like with one'riflanadi. Mehnat resources with the human factor unitsqqoslash in regard more as a olg'a qfrom adam qo'flush is that to say it is, human factor concept o'zida qanday is limited to o'zida hugs. His units'the secret circle the people of the society, the main wealth toe'become qaralmaydi, but then the development process compared tashqi a factor as it is understood. Also come thqneedless adi, this is limited to our of our society development level ko'rsat is.

Human factor – political-Iqtisodiy terms, the modern general theory of the subject, mehnat ergonomic and pedagogy election ruhiyat of, psychology. The human factor e'tibor

avtoritar, ma'muriy-bureaucratic homethearuv methods with achieved toe'which lmas social-Iqtisodiy development accelerate with o'zaro garden'may be justified.

Homeqaruvning ma'muriy in the system, the human factor ahamiyatiga surface qof the ara, the present andthetda its pharynx of the rejection you knew was, so'z without obey to either'settings,thedata was on, as a result, the person the society is interested in, mehnatkashlarning while the general public mathesad and the interests o'zlashtirilardi and this whole home,thearuv of the system hfrom ed ortiq centralized and byurakratlashishi with the gardens'greenhouses. Ayni andthetda, hometo thearuvning iqtisodiy method o'teeth ko'rsat demonstrates, the human factor faollashtirmasdan stand and it achieved toe'was lmas.

It's yaqqbuy taste'i as her different countries in new technologies in use, theariya that a different approach to their work thqto arib salohof iyat athon iqtisodiyotida equal was not ko'to rsat can. O'after moving of the century' o'is central in G'arbiy Europe and AQSh work stqarib coming iqtisodiy salohiyat of oneqqoslanganda it G'arbiy to europe , compared with AQShda much yuqori at the level of the toe'ldi. Such hpenis causes lekarzemthepros maqsad 50-years in Stanford University (AQSh) hamda European experts with the participation of all athon the scientific executed at check o'- check-in of passengers. This verification lekarzemq ko'rsat demonstrates, AQSh and G'arbiy European mahsuldorligi o'in rtasi farthe funds' with ta'service minlash the level of the garden'liq is not. Ko'pgina European enterprises iqtisodiy the effectiveness of the main foundations in the level of a different toe'lish to tryingaramasdan, AQshda the same so directory than from three to two times lower was. Such hpenis suddenly a to'g'settings understand european enterprises in qo'llanilayotgan homethearuv in the style of theolontryingwas possible that it was.

So qtwisted, the staff of the chief of thearib of the new style ahamiyati o'a worthy typical homeqaruv technology as work ndqto arib attracted qresearched resources iqtisodiy effective maximum at the level of ta'care minlash take come o'zini's whole world miqyosin in officially recognized to get managed.

Yuqori's thoughts to summarize members of the "human factor" the concept of thehouse total ta'reef give you can:

Human factor – umumlashgan concept toe'become, human activity mohof iyat can toe'present hamma ko'to rinib, individual level or mehnat and any primeq, a team level its social, creative activity hamda human activities possible toe'present barhca oqibatlarini o'z into gets.

“Human factor” , the concept of “subjective factor”, “personal factors”, “social factors”, “man” such as concepts with the garden'liq, but this with along their her one with big and small at the level of farq qwill ilar. Philosophical nuthetaiga from the “human factor” “a man have'i” the concept of yaqin is, because “human factor”of the basic concept – man role, its activity on the basis of active out is out. Human factors , most muhim structural komponenta the toe'become quyidagilar hisoblanadi: social-ruhiy quality (requirements, interests, motives, qadriyatli either'are nalisth and homein theit was many years ago), general culture level: professionalism and raqobatchilik, reliability, of an individual who has an undisciplined and ma'suliyatlilik level, careers and guruhs o'in rtasi o'zaro harakat and gentleon thehorse of the results, the collective “ta'education”, current hpenis (mehnat koopertsiyasining synergistic ta'secret, ma'naviy-ruhiy I havetheeducation, the team “ruhi”, as you want and ma'suliyat hissi, leadership and generalthewas many years ago).

Conclusion. Society taraqqiyoti during ko'pgina sciences of the human variety, jihatdan – biological, ruhiy, philosophical, iqtisodiy and homeqa jihfrom atlar o'rga were. His o'worthy of specific features, activity of maqsadi, come stq,work, nature , and all- sides, chuqur tahlil qwas twisted. most mashhur scientists, politicians, historical persons, all o'zlar of ta'limot in man the problem of bypassing o'those who tma. So toe'in lsa, human problem to'la he charged are not. After all, man mohwho iyat social-historical and cultural creatures as her-a new historical conditions o'o z chuqurraq to realize, human mohof iyat listed in'native to, such as sttheto arib intilaveradi.

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The concept of human temperament and its specific features

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Abstract. In this article, the concept of temperament and its specific features are studied human birth, its usefulness and practical importance are studied.

Keywords: Temperament, manners, character, abilities, human psychology.

To enter. Certain features of the character from the conditions of life, social environment, and the feature of the person's work come from many intraoperative and natural character, temperament is determined.

Man's conduct of the understanding ko'pgina theory created. In particular, philosophers themy adi times since the person of the activity of the source and methodology'zg'atuvchi the source of the character to attempt those who. Of them some opinion, human conduct basic reason his qanoatlanishga ambitions (gedonizm doctrine). TWENTIETH century American psychologist direction is bixevorizm wide meshhur if gone, his research complex in the person of conduct various forms of be, they tashqi muhhis dog - stimulating factors in the body's reactions to a set as is understood.

The main part.

“Temperament” of the concept of Latin “temperament drum” - thename of the appropriate ratio, that ratio so'th zdan comeqqan. That is, consists of a set of dynamic and specific features of the person and the emotional side of its activities, as well as yield reflects the hulk.

Man needs come thqib, his manners explain which theories ko'pro ofthe development found. Such a theory of the most famous authors A. Maslov, e. kat, D. Nac Klelland, F. Gertsburg and the other a qator are scientists.

For example, good haq get to work who do not professionals employee incomeq a new job looking for muqsaws. Such behavior of the reason working from theoniqmasin we have, accomplish the task by the chamber of interest because of the decreasein ehthymol, the head with their relationship to the violation, the team in the conditions o'since zgarib and colleagues with relations in tension because of the severity and other reasons to be can.

Xulq-hosts around the person-muhdog o'the effects of b to form into zaro consists ofo'become a qfactors toe atorg'liq bo'ladi. Shaxsi and his hulq-hosts gives the description of many main factors that include the following:

- the person's natural hususiyatlari his o'a worthy typical pishologik hususiyatlari;
- eholdest and largesteitherj, causes, qtrailthesystem works;
- the person hometo thearib to the system, its “-image”.

Temperament of the most popular types (sangvinik, melanxolik, flegmatik and xolerik) bc previous century,like Hippocrates by introduced qresearched bo'become, their names hanuzgacha saqlanga thebody, but the content o'zga were.

Disposition of the person o'worthy distinctive features from the set is bo'to become, to them his business dynamic and ha issi edge, also xulq-hosts of the resonance has a number , and them in thehouse namoeithern bo'ladi:

- xoleriklarda - severe reactions, is the center ofthesocial, the mood dramatically the exchange, beqamong efficacy and general harakatchanlik with namoeithern bo'ladi;
- rational - (behavior-harakat of to'g'will rilik) with characterized;
- in flegmatik - procrastination, barqamong efficacy, biqiqsocial, hissi a state tashthebee small namoeithern qilma not, gentlehof bereavement mantitheinternational standard with differs;
- in melanxolik - betheamong efficacy, easily impressed, odamshavanda not, hatto trivial of things,aworld , and whereqfrom ea hat chuqur lowershoots with separated;
- sangvinik in - harakatchanlik, the impression replace to stand the batter, irritability, odamshavandalik with separated is.

Temperament of the list o'built in the us this kind ofthe worldi than bartheis among the bo'become, muhdog and education in the effects of o'zgarib less bo'ysunadi. Shit with

along they are the person on the content side, theadriyatlari and eh,oldest and largestof eitherof the j expression does not.

19of 40-years, a guruh american scientists Ayzenk G. rahbar temperament , the concept of above looking outlgan two factors: ekstraversiya and emotionally barqarorlikning o'zaro toeg'liq, stained result as whoqin qwere twisted. This guruh in the person of superior levels of temperament lekarzethepros bo'citizens test work stqdi.

Most ko'p tarqthe alga and mashhur tests: mm as Kettella and hometheis was many years ago. Shaxsi've tempered Ient come thqib, its qanday reaction that give to know the temperament of the positive xususiyatlariga to rely on and the negative features to an end to give the possibility of poses. For example, the xolerik tension politelasocial and bosinqmore with the answer you give, the flegmatik affairs stagnant active interaction, interaction impressive theara by-qarshi methodology'yish, melanjolik's qcannotg'usi to the optimist (optimism) with overcome can be. Psychology frequently noted theas twisted, sangvinik the references tayeitherrlashga usually ko'pinch draft qisqarti by eitherza they eitheror them this mutqo eitherzmaydilar, xoleriks ko'pinch attention because of simple mistakes yo'l methodology'of yadi, are flegmatik while andthetning o'tib that goes to paytheama after, work late and be completed in may.

ShI qilish, staff individual-psychological hususiyatlarini to know it with tryinganday in circulation bo'lish the shape of to'g'settings to select eitherrda I will.

Character hususiyatlari certain conditions, haeithertning social environment and the person's work hususiyatidan come thqadi and ko'p jihatdan natural character, temperament by is determined.

Natural character with toeg'liq bo'present in the person of the psychological hususiyatlari again a muhim properties - qobiliyatlarni up will.

Qobiliyatlar the person's knowledge, ko'are nikma and skills dressing theilish speed and his certain types of activities you perform to the possibility with the set.

Sh've axsi second factor or structural part of its eholdest and largest either of the j, of reason, the daughter of the work system, that is, of the person in the field of the causes, what are the appreciation of character there is, qabul qilinadigan qamong to explain it helps.

Sh've axsi hulq-hosts of the set which gives the third structural parts management system or “-” concept is. His essence of every one of one's own originality, unique, o'z “” a nest of his qthat twisted, person ozini o'in tmish, the following and the da and in the future qanday case, ko'browsing, isee the means of reaching it is. This concept of the person o'zi haqida, o'z qtrail the work, it, mo'ljallari, ozini ozi hthe in urma qbe twisted, to himself bo'present belief haqida imagination o'z into gets. This concept of the operation, either or practical mohiyat of that iboratki, us around the universe with bo'ladi, who 's all our relationship o'z “” imiz the ko'browsing on the basis of, audience reaction of the person o'z reaction with qanday likely coming from the fact comes thqib organization is.

“-Image”'s barthe efficiency among the human xulq-hosts of the ministry consistent and barthe or ligning condition hisoblanadi. The person with certain hususiyatlar set o'to rnatish, and it is constant on the basis of sathelip to stand strives. Bit features its qanday applying, mohiyat the outline gives you. The person o'zini his audience with o'z relations are those of the imagination of the participating'indisi to muvofiq up will, o'worthy o'zi and home from the to it was many years ago baho gives. A qator in xolni people you lens info o'z to imagine muvofiq if it comes, it denying qbe twisted can and noto'g'settings either or hatto either lg'on the data to believe (if they “-image”'ha muvofiq come in) can.

The human mind o'z of the image, o'zini's real “” accounted for htown imo qtwisted psychological mechanism, there is bo'ladi. They are the person with the psychological balance saqpros and its psychological “comfort” for necessary bo'ladi. This with along the engine recognition that the idi is a gentlehof bereavement perception to kiyinlashtirishi can, because they created an internal image, the person o'zi haqida imagination of the unity breaks.

This process balmn enough at the level of complex, sometimes og'settingsq,li bo'become, in a few clickqichda occur bo'ladi and of man, the whole of life, bo'participation continue will, that social guruhs, the order of a simple idea and change someone, the

sameqsa in society social yo'nalish the exchange is a simple idea and someone happened bo'ladi. The following and the da society ro'y give either after moving processes either social way-y -o' settings qs o'zgarib it with the to eg'liq bo'become, the person on the norms and mo'ljallari o'in zgarib o'z expression finds. In practice her a man into the body of that come on the market iqtisodiy either the oldest and largest in the context of society o'z o'the mi qidir and to find forced bo'l.qat, ko'pgina qadriyat larga qfrom I baho to give happen bo'l.qat, as a result of the person o'worthy-o'zi baiho giving in the process of hat islamis being formed to go to get hot.

The formation of the goals of the enterprise managers in the management process and how to achieve them direct the planning, organization, promotion, computer control equipment and many times will take the running of your country.

They manage the activities of enterprises on production planning work was taksimlash pogona follows :

- top management in pogona – strategic and perspektiv planning;
- middle management in pogona – current planning;
- the lower management in pogona – work out up to (operational management).

Operational management directly work out of jaraen, new organization daily life management with weightloss measures uz into gets. Boshkacha kila in words, operational management of the current plan of implementation increase (to life applied was) is , and it mainly cocktail unumdrligini to increase the aims of would. Operational management of the current plan in the prescribed measures for the current year on taksimlash was (organization size and work out of kulami to karab kvartal, monthly , and even the 10 - day and week plans are formed).

Management of this function is planned in the matter, the powers that be (in the organization of the resources of foydlanish limited legal)to the top from below karab signals and to taksimlash referring keeps. This process of the roof, the meaning with the organization within the framework of done , which is a cocktail of taksimoti uzginasidir. Therefore, the organization of the successful functioning will show he sees the plan after the organization of the function perform increase chog'ida the ground will create.

Control – the organization's goals progress ta'minlash that is a process. T ito'xtovsiz form problems get more complicated departure before identify and successful activity stimulate in order to methodology'is llab. Control three types of bo'linadi :

a) the term from the previous control – plan indicators, issues and powers o'zaro mosliligini work start before check;

b) current control – the work being started after bo'ysunuvchilarning mehnat activity of the immediate - headedq by be observed;

v) xulosaviy control – ish completion after it or him separated from andqt is the completion of bo'from the present, then bo'ysunuvchilarning directly headedqqa hisobot they give.

The general purpose of the organization together with the mutual relations in the direction of the actions the actions the various components (elements) if they show successful or productive activity, on the basis of a common denominator of the relationship is set. Turlichaligi come to a common denominator come from the roots of viewpoint have been necessary. People have been soxibi different viewpoint of the organization structure to the incoming leaders, experts, working simple-workers. The structure of their organization to incoming machines, lathes, production buildings, weapons work and x.k.the next step which set of different people from around the world (behavior-actions of relations), say ilgaridan get (setting, planning) probability nature, it is important to specify exactly what that is. Therefore, to achieve the overall objective rejalashtirsh issues are to be applied where the organization to remain in control is a common behavior for all on-the rules of actions (the common denominator) production will be necessary. At times like this that refers to the rules of law or the principle of management of the organization also.

We the above rules, the law, understanding the principles of network may not aim to give a single description. Just let them have made to the analysis of the role of the organization in the management process actions are just that.

Above we suggested the same approach to determine the boundaries of the management process three than not. In fact, various scientists engaged in knowledge

management, the heads of organizations experienced murakkb (practice management professionals), their own levels, experience of viewpoint, who applied methods of management and leadership style and the situation show the mean concentration of the organization's activities or they may offer different content tamoyilarlarining manage proceeding from conditions may apply.

According to the law on the enterprise management enterprise is carried out. One of the principles of this law envisaged in the whole team to make important decisions and to carry out control and its organizations to take part in it with the way they performed self-management principle.

Management organizational structures of the main types of linear and functional type. Them to be attached to on the basis of various different linear-functional structures of the content you will find.

Linear structures its lower management of the unit is the upper stage of the head to direct bo'ysunushi with characterized. Linear structure , each with a staff of one to the head of subject and high system with only it by bound will be. linear structures positive side of his simple, reliable, is kamxarj. Ter a leader of the entire work team activities are the results of on responsible. This strategy and the current decision to accept to law markazlashishiga out comes.

Functional structure – management function functional joints and the head between the distribution leads to is based on. It management for a complex boost and specialization development with associated without being into come.

Chiziqli-shtabli structures, linear structures on the basis of made is, but the guidance of the lower tier having each of the unit has some important problems on staff is made up. Staff of qualified decisions to prepare, but the linear structure of the head of the approval, the lower level is sent. It staff recommendations koordinatsiya makes, coordinates , and as a result management of the quality of xshilanadi, but avzifalar the amount of a lot is.

Management the organization of matriza with structure in project or program of the head of the activity of the freedom it provides, them before , has put the issues targeted the

solution is. Work of the organization to be on the head of a responsibility is determined, their performance of the term, the final results on the head of responsibility will determine. Market economy conditions, the management of the apparatus specified level or decrease, of governance at various levels, and each of the zveno on the border of the large level functions and the functions of clear separation, people, economy, enterprises (firms) the network of economic independence to ensure the opportunity that gives the new organizational structure is formed.

Management organizational structure in the formation of management of bounce and the zveno of the number, linear and functional management of markazlashuv level, management of the department and functions of the composition, one to the head on who comes to the subject directed to the number of on the basis of required. Management system in the bounce how much are order from the top down and the information down up signals that so difficult is. Command and information transmission in the process of breaking the risk is so high it is. This is the reason for the management of the organizational structure loyixalashtirish and improved process control of the level number of the optimal to be to strive it is necessary.

The administrative apparatus of the structure of the basic requirements for its operativligidadir. The apparatus structure so at the level of flexible and simple to be that the management system of the decision to accept to and of it out increase should. The operative with the business of launching a reliable order is associated. This means management apparatus, information transmission of the correctness guarantee to give the transferred data btszilishiga the way put not you should, management system, communication is continuous, and that ensure should.

Perfect or democratic structure - this Veber by offered was finished, and then nafakat work out, but also community organizations in a wide range of do and uz to the composition of the following description takes: the cocktail specialization, ash ostidagilar the career looking buysunadi of, certain specified liabilities and responsibilities, established procedures, and treatments of the system of relationship egasizlantirmok, service from the stairs of the servants of the qualification on the basis of engage, the xokimlik centralized,

with abilities that are reporting. That are seen as the name suggests, the organization's bureaucratic structure of all the symptoms above are listed to the management of mechanical structure description tugri comes. Management in this model, half of the century, many in the period of the priority remains to come. Close-yaqinlargacha, wide do in firms' organizational procedures, types of many or bit is at the level of the us are combined: vazifaviy, regular, regular-shtabli, by divizion. This structure of society, industrial tarakkietini revive shows.

The organization, the size of the composition to it the effects of high seen in the structure of a description with weightloss: complex, formal and nomarkazlashish. Naturally, assuming that remain if the firm or corporation of a few hundred thousand servants, to have would, then it is difficult to content, that is, large in number or by divizion bulinmalariga able will be. This structure of the mechanical type. Complex vaziftdan out of the only way - organic content integration from is. The organization size and centralized in the range of negative let weightloss out there. A firm small large doses if it is the case management centralized it is. You large doses, the higher management of all types of control is complete you can, so for the representation of a kismi to the lower level give forced will be.

Management functions from another one – band management with territorial management and the ratio of ta'is minlash. Her a directory how a network (in the sector) to enter. The same time it is a district in the territory of that particular its place in local work release - territorial complex enters. Management in the process, this function also territorial, also the network of interests will be keeping should. The network in the administrative functions necessary. This is you network “disappear” only for technical and technology policy implementation to enhance and the entire network is attributed are other issues to settle to is.

However, at the same time, management of territorial functions are also necessary. This function is a particular district, the region of the territory located in the various sectors (sector thisha) owned enterprises, the activities of coordinates, rational contacts inserted in taominlaydi. Territorial taxation office, the leadership of the idea of loss, noratsional the fall to reduce and ultimately efficiency level of increase in the opportunity it gives.

The management structure to work out the structure with also characterized. Thus, the management of the organization of the first and defining factor in the work out process is is. It mutually the main, auxiliary and service provider from the process is if, this process is and the staff between labor distribution require will. Shit in order worked out to be and to them in particular that the management apparatus is formed.

Conclusion. Q policyishloq economy enterprises management effectiveness in increasing the following follow to need:

- social, community and personal interests that purpose in accordance with the combination into account taking without the economic conditions of the system of improvement;
- science-technical progress, the results introduced , which without the rural economy intensivlashtirish he consistently out increase; material-technical base strengthening;
- main and working capital from the fund, labor resources, effective use, labor productivity increase, rural, farm products quality and improve;
- save-to tergab mode and material interest of the principle of implementation of the increase;
- market economy requirements into account taking without work to manage forms of improvement;
- the peasants and farmers of their labor to the results possess to be sure, poses , and others.

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BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF BOSQICHIDA MATEMATIKA FANI BOYICHA O'QUV KONTENTINI SHAKLLANTIRISH

Gadaeva Tamara Narzullaevna

Jizzax shaxri 22-kimyo,biologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashtirilgan
umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi

Аннотация. Ushbu ishda boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun matematika fanini o'qitish jarayoni, uning o'quv kontentinishi tashkil etish masalasiga katta e'tibor berilgan. Yangi axborot texnologiya dasturiy vosita va uning imkoniyatlari haqida ma'lumot keltirilgan.

Калит so'zlar: o'quv jarayoni, shakl, burchak, axborot texnologiyalar, o'quv kontent.

Аннотация. В данной работе большое внимание уделено вопросу о процессе составления учебника по математике для учащихся начальных классов, организации его учебного содержания. Представлена информация о новом информационном технологическом программном средстве и его возможностях.

Ключевые слова: учебный процесс, форма, угол, информационные технологии, учебное содержание.

Abstract. In this work, great attention was paid to the question of the process of teaching mathematics for elementary students, the organization of its educational content. The new information technology is presented information about the software tool and its capabilities.

Keywords: educational process, form, angle, information technology, educational content.

Jamiyatning kelajagini ta'minlaydigan va shakllantiradigan o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodni bilimli, o'zining Vatanini sevadigan va milliy qadriyatlarni hurmat qiladigan, mehnatash va jismonan baquvvat qilib tarbiyalash eng muhim masalalardan biridir. Aynan, shu fikrni Prezident Sh.Mirziyoyev ta'kidlab o'tgan.

Maktab o'quvchilarining bilimi va ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish, ularni milliy hamda umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga sodiqlik ruhida tarbiyalash, o'qituvchi kasbi nufuzini va pedagoglarning sifat tarkibini oshirish, darsliklar va o'quv metodik majmualarni zamon

talablari asosida takomillashtirish, maktab ta'limi muassasalarining xalqaro standartlarga javob beradigan zamonaviy modellarini barpo etish maqsadida, shuningdek, 2022 — 2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan YAngi O'zbekistonning Taraqqiyot strategiyasini «Inson qadrini ulug'lash va faol mahalla yili»da amalga oshirishga oid [davlat dasturiga](#) muvofiq:

1. 2022 — 2026 yillarda maktab ta'limini rivojlantirish bo'yicha milliy dastur [1- ilovaga](#) muvofiq tasdiqlansin.

2. Quyidagilar Rivojlantirish dasturining asosiy yo'nalishlari etib belgilansin:

maktab ta'limiga ilg'or xalqaro tajribalar asosida ishlab chiqilgan Milliy o'quv dasturini to'laqonli joriy etish hamda mahalliy va xorijiy mualliflar tomonidan yaratilgan zamonaviy darsliklarni amaliyotga kiritish;

jamiyatda o'qituvchi kasbi nufuzini oshirish, pedagoglar uchun qulay ijtimoiy sharoitlar yaratish va mehnatini munosib rag'batlantirish;

o'qituvchilarning yoshlarga ta'lim va tarbiya berishdagi mas'uliyatini, doimiy kasbiy rivojlanishdagi talabchanligini oshirish;

umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalari uchun milliy kadrlar zaxirasini shakllantirish, ilg'or maktab direktori va namunali o'qituvchi mezonlarini ishlab chiqish hamda ular asosida rahbar va pedagog kadrlar faoliyatini baholab borish;

o'quvchilarning bo'sh vaqtlarini mazmunli tashkil etish, ularni kasblarga yo'naltirish tizimini takomillashtirish;

darslik va ularning mazmuniga aynan shu erda qayd etilgan:

Milliy dastur. 1-ilovasi. 6-bandi. O'qituvchilarning ilg'or tajribasi va faoliyatida qo'llagan zamonaviy metodikalarni ommalashtirish.

Bunda quyidagilar nazarda tutilgan:

1. Ilg'or tajribaga ega bo'lgan va faoliyatida zamonaviy metodikalarni qo'llaydigan o'qituvchilarni aniqlash tartibini ishlab chiqish va xalq ta'limi vaziri buyrug'i bilan tasdiqlash.

2. Ilg'or tajribaga ega bo'lgan va faoliyatida zamonaviy metodikalarni qo'llaydigan o'qituvchilar ro'yxatini shakllantirish.

3. O'qituvchilarning ilg'or tajribasi va zamonaviy metodikalarini ommalashtirish.

Ushbu ishda boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarga matematika fanining o'quv qontentinini tushuntirish misrlariga e'tibor qaratsak.

Insonning hotirasi eng katta hajmda aynan shaklli ma'lumotlar orqali eslab qolishi osondir. SHuning uchun biz mantiqiy fikrlashning birinchi bosqichi sifatida shakllarni tanib olish mashqi ko'rib chiqamiz.

1-rasm. Aylana shakllarni ajrating

Keltirilgan tasvirli ma'lumotlardan maktab o'quvchilarda shakllarni bilan ishlash, ularning shaklini eslab qolish va tasavvuriga saqlash maqsadida davriy qaytarilishi maqsadga muvofik bo'lardi.

Qo'shimcha manbalarni o'rganish uchun mustaqil turli shakllardagi manbalarni o'rganish, ularning qo'llanish usullari va yasalgan manbalar to'g'risida ma'lumotga ega bo'lishga imkoniyat yaratiladi. Mana shu shaklar orqali o'quvchilarda yangi tushuncha xosil qilishga erishamiz.

Keyingi qadam burchaklar va ularni tasniflash, umumiy ko'rinishi va amaliy qo'llanilishi to'g'risida ma'lumotga ega bo'lish masalasi belgilangan.

2-rasm. To'g'ri burchakni toping.

Rasmda keltirilgan 8 ta turli hil burchaklarning orasida aytilgan javobni topish, keyinroq esa boshqa turdagi burchaklarni aniqlash va ularni tasavvurida aks ettirilishiga katta ahamiyatga ega. Inson atrifidagi bino-inshoatlarni va buromlarning birinchi navbatda ularning burchaklar orqali baholaydi.

Matematika fanini o'rganish uchun elektron dasturiy vositalar xam yaratilmoqda. Uning misoli sifatida 1-sinf uchun darslik keltirilgan.

3-rasm. 1-sinf o'quvchilar uchun Matematika elektron darsligi

4-rasm. 1-sinf Matematika elektron darslik mundarijasi

Ushbu darslik o'zbek tilida bo'lib shquv material juda sodda va osongina tushunadigan shaklda berilgan. O'quv kontent izchil shakllantirilgan va talaffuz nuqtai nazardan ham juda yaxshi tayyorlangan.

Dastur ishlashi ham juda osongina va texnik nuqtai nazardan deyarli muammosiz tayyorlangan. Dizayn va uning talqini biroz yangicha qarashlarga fikrlar mavjudligi va qayta ishlanishi amalga oshirilsa yaxshi bo'lardi. Boshqa tomondan, darslikda axborot texnologiya vositalari bilan mustaqil tarzda ishlash ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish maqsadida foydalanilsh juda o'rinli bo'lardi.

Xulosa shuki, dunyoni taqqoslash va uni o'rganish uchun matematika fanining asoslarini yaxshi tushunish, amalda qo'llash imkoniyatidan keng foydalanish boshqa fanlardan yaxshi o'zlashtirishna turtki bo'ladi.

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ILMIY NASHRLAR MARKAZI

СТРАТЕГИЯ ИНТЕРНЕТ-МАРКЕТИНГА

INTERNET MARKETING STRATEGY

INTERNET MARKETING STRATEGIYASI

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Аннотация: В статье в основном говорится о стратегии интернет-маркетинга и маркетинговой деятельности.

Ключевые слова: маркетинговая деятельность, стратегия, маркетинговая среда, финансовый риск, маркетинговые исследования

Аннотация: Мақолада асосан internet marketing strategiyasi va marketing faoliyati ҳақида айтиб ўтилган

Калм сўзлар: marketing faoliyati, strategiya, marketing muhiti, moliyaviy xavf, marketing tadqiqoti

Annotation: The article mainly talks about internet marketing strategy and marketing activities.

Keywords: marketing activities, strategy, marketing environment, financial risk, marketing research

В процессе анализа, планирования, реализации и контроля эффективности маркетинговой деятельности необходима различная информация об окружающей маркетинговой среде и внутренней среде предприятия. Маркетинговые исследования – это деятельность, связанная с систематическим сбором, анализом и представлением информации о различных аспектах маркетинговой деятельности. Маркетинговые исследования — это функция, которая посредством информации связывает предприятие с рынками, потребителями, конкурентами и всеми элементами внешней маркетинговой среды. Современная, полезная и полная информация дает компании следующие возможности::

- снижение финансового риска и риска нанесения ущерба репутации компании;
- иметь конкурентные преимущества;

- следить за маркетинговой средой;
- координация стратегии;
- оценка эффективности;
- повысить интуицию менеджеров.

Компания проводит маркетинговые исследования самостоятельно или силами отдела маркетинга или специализированных организаций. К типичным видам маркетинговых исследований относятся:

- ♣ Изучить особенности рынка;
- ♣ Измерение рыночных возможностей;
- ♣ Анализ распределения рыночных долей предприятий;
- ♣ Анализ продаж;
- ♣ Изучить тенденции деловой активности;
- ♣ Изучение продукции конкурентов;
- ♣ Изучить отношение к новому товару и его размеру;
- ♣ Долгосрочное прогнозирование спроса и цен;
- ♣ Изучение ценовой политики конкурентов и т.д.

Цель, задачи и направления маркетинговых исследований Цель и задачи маркетинговых исследований направлены на выявление проблемы, изучение и рекомендацию объекта, процесса или ситуации, обнаружение закономерностей и составление прогнозов. В зависимости от характера целей маркетинговых исследований можно выделить три важных направления маркетинговых исследований:

- ♣ поисковые исследования – исследования, направленные на сбор необходимой информации для углубленного изучения проблем и предположений (гипотез);

- ♣ описательные исследования – исследования, направленные на описание проблем, ситуаций, объектов и процессов;

- ♣ рандомизированные исследования – исследования, проводимые с целью проверки причинно-следственных гипотез.

Направления маркетинговых исследований можно охарактеризовать в зависимости от объекта исследования, например, изучение рынка, отдельных элементов маркетингового комплекса (товар, цена, продвижение, сбыт). Кроме того, маркетинговые исследования включают изучение макросреды на компоненты, влияющие на маркетинговую деятельность.

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Bargi boru guli yo'q, guli boru bargi yo'q:**Qoraqobiq o'simligining tuzilishi, tinim davri, hayot sikli va xususiyatlari**

Nargizaxon Ibrohimova Iqboljon qizi

Andijon davlat universiteti biologiya ta'lim yo'nalishi talabasi

Annotasiya: Ushbu maqola Qoraqobiq (qoravaroq) o'simligining tuzilishi va xususiyatlari haqida.

Kalit so'zlar: Qoraqobiq, tinim davri, chuchmomadoshlar, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi, alkaloidlar, galantamin, Omonqora qoraqobig'i

Qoraqobiqlar (Ungernialar)- chuchmomadoshlarga mansub ko'p yillik piyozboshli o'tlardir. Ularning piyozboshi tuxumsimon, uzunligi 7-10 sm, usti ko'p qavatli qoraqo'ng'ir qobiqlar bilan o'ralgan. Uning nomi aynan shu xususiyati bilan bog'liq. Barglari qalin, keng, qalami, eni 1-2 sm, uzunligi esa 25-40 sm, har bir piyozboshdan martning birinchi yarmidan boshlab 10-12 tagacha barg o'sib chiqadi va ular aprelning ikkinchi yarmida voyaga yetadi.

Qoraqobiqlar O'rta Osiyo uchun hos o'simliklar bo'lib boshqa yerda uchramaydi. Ular asosan adirning yuqori qismida va tog'larda o'sib, har xil ko'lamdagi qoraqobiqzorlarni hosil qiladi. Qoraqobiqzorlarni, ayniqsa, mart oyida va aprelning birinchi yarmida uzoq-uzoqlardan ham ko'rish mumkin. Chunki bu davrda tog' yonbag'rlaridagi boshqa o'tlar hali yaxshi o'smagan bo'lib, qoraqobiqlar ko'k-yashil "orolchalar" shaklida juda aniq ko'rinadi. Lekin iyunga kelgach bu qoraqobiqzorlardan asar ham qolmaydi. Chunki yomg'irli fasllar tugab saratonning issiq kunlari boshlangach, uning barglari qurib shamolda uchib ketadi, bu payt o'simlik piyozi yozgi "uyquga" kiradi.

Avgustning ikkinchi yarmi va sentabr boshlarida tog'lar, kechalari ancha salqin bo'lib, ba'zi yerlarga uncha-muncha yomg'ir ham yog'ib o'tadi. Bu davrda qoraqobiq yana "uyg'onadi". Lekin piyozboshdan endi ko'k yashil burglar emas, balki sarg'ish bargsiz poya o'sib chiqadi. Bu poyaning uchida 7-9 ta gul ochiladi. Qoraqobiq mevasi sentabrning oxirida pishadi. Urug'I tarqalib bo'lgach, uning poyasi ham quriydi va qoraqobiq ikkinchi bor "uyquga" kiradi.

Demak O'rta Osiyo sharoitida o'sadigan ko'p yillik o'simliklar bir yilda faqat bir marta qishki uyquga kirsam, qoraqobiqlar ikki marta, yozgi va qishki uyquga kiradi.

O'zbekiston Fanlar Akademiyasi O'simlik moddalari kimyosi institutida olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijasida qoraqobiqlarning ildizi, bargi va mevalarida ko'p

miqdorda alkaloidlar borligi aniqlangan. Qoraqobiqlardan ajratib olingan alkaloidlardan galantamin alkaloidi alohida o'rinni egallaydi. Bu alkaloid hammasidan ko'ra omonqora qoraqobig'ida (*Ungernia viktoris*) ko'proq bo'ladi. Uning bargidagi galantamin miqdori 0,15% ga yetadi.

Galantamin preparati poliomielit kasalligining qoldiq holatlarini davolashda foydalaniladi.

O'zbekistonda foydali o'simliklar bilan bir qatorda zaxarli o'tlar ham oz emas. Bunday o'tlardan ko'pincha uy hayvonlari va ba'zan odamlar ham zaxarlanishlari mumkin. Zaxarli o'simliklar Respublikamizning turli burchaklarida tabiiy sharoitda va ekin maydonlarida uchrab turadi.

Foydali va zaxarli o'tlarni tanish, ularning hususiyatlari nimada ekanligini bilish, bunday o'simliklardan kasallanishning oldini olish va ularga qarshi samarali kurash choralarini bilish, o'simliklar florasidan unumli foydalanishga undaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Dorivor o'simliklar florasini va sistematikasi ; L.A. Botirova, D.M. Tagayeva; Guliston-2021.-100 bet
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3. O'zbekiston florasini 1-6 tom
4. Qiziqarli botanika; M. Nabiyeu; T. Odilov; O'. Prator; G'. Shermator; Toshkent-1975

Internet manbalari

5. www.ziyonet.uz;
6. www.floranimal.ru.
7. www.fizrast.ucoz.ru

TOG'AY MUROD ASARLARIDA MILLIY QAHRAMON MASALASI**Qodirova Dilnoza Alisher qizi****Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat****o'zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti magistranti**

Annotatsiya: maqolada Tog'ay Murod asarlarida, aniqrog'i hikoya va qissalarida milliylik tasvirining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari haqida ba'zi fikr va xulosalar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: milliylik, qissa, an'ana va urf-odatlar, tasvir, badiiy tahlil

Dunyoda millatlar va elatlar qanchalik ko'p bo'lmasin, shoir va yozuvchilar ham shunchalik yetarli. Lekin har bir qushning o'z xonishi bo'lgani kabi har bir shoir va yozuvchining ham o'z ijod yo'li va o'ziga xos uslubi mavjuddir. Birinchi prezidentimiz I.A. Karimov o'zining "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch" asarida shoir va yozuvchilarni inson ruhining muhandislari deya ta'riflaydilar. Jamiyatimizda ijodkorlarning, ya'ni yozuvchi va shoirlarning qadim zamonlardan o'rni bo'lak bo'lib kelganligi hech kimga sir emas. Sho'ro tuzumida esa ularning xo'rlangani-yu xorlanganini ham bilamiz. Ozgina xat-savodni tanigan, ijod qilishni ko'ngliga tuggan yosh ijodkorlarning ham boshlariga qanday ko'rgiliklar yog'ilmadi deysiz.

- "Men bir qora kunda tug'ildim,
Tug'ildim-u shu on bo'g'ildim", - degan edi shoir H.Olimjon

Lekin bunday qora kunlarning tugashiga umid qilib yashagan "qora" xalqimiz, o'z niyatiga yetdi. Barcha ozod davlatlar qatori biz ham o'z erkimizni qo'lga kiritdik.

Bu mustaqillik yo'lida esa jon kuydirgan qanchadan qancha jadidchilarimiz, yosh, biz bilgan va bilmagan ijodkorlarimiz o'z jonlarini qurbon qilishdi. Chor Rossiyasi hukmronligi davrida kitob u yoqda tursin, oddiy qog'ozlarga ham ijod qilolmagan yozuvchilarimiz qancha edi?! Lekin bu qora kunlar o'tib, bizning tomonlarda quyosh porladi. O'zbek

romanchiligiga asos solindi, ilk o‘zbek teatrlari, pyesalari qo‘yila boshlandi. Albatta, bular jadidchilarimiz tomonida 1900-1920 yillarda amalga oshirilgan ishlar bo‘lsa-da, jadidchilarimizning jasorati, shijoat va qat‘iyati orqasidan qilingan ishlar edi. Sekin-astalik bilan adabiyotimiz rivojlana boshlanadi. Avval jadidchilarimiz, so‘ngra XX asrning 30-40 yillarida o‘z ijod namunalari bilan gullashni boshlagan bir qator shoir va yozuvchilarimiz shular jumlasidandir. O‘tgan asrning 70-80-yillarida esa o‘zbek adabiyotida Murod Muhammad Do‘st, Xayriddin Sulton, Erkin A‘zam va Tog‘ay Murod kabi bir qator yangi nomlar paydo bo‘ldi.

Yuqorida nomi keltirilgan adiblarimiz ichidan esa tadqiqotimizning asosiy mavzusi bo‘lgan Tog‘ay Murod haqida so‘z boshlaymiz. Milliylik degan tushuncha har bir davrdagi o‘ziga xoslikni saqlab qolishga yordam beruvchi eng muhim asos. Ya‘ni milliylik asarning har tomonlama o‘qishli bo‘lishini ta‘minlovchi bo‘lakdir. Internet manbalarida yana shunday tushunchalar ham borki, “milliylik turli xalqlar adabiyotlar o‘rtasida to‘siq emas balki adabiyotlarning yashash tarzidir. Umuminsoniy muammolar har bir xalq adabiyotida takrorlanmas o‘ziga xos o‘ziga xos milliy xususiyatlarda namoyon bo‘ladi. Adabiyot va san‘atning milliyliги umuminsoniy mohiyatga egadir. Umuminsoniylik milliylikning mohiyatidir, milliylik esa umuminsoniylikning namoyon bo‘lishidir. Nihoyat, adabiyotning umuminsoniyliги milliy xususiyatlarini yo‘qolib borishi hisobiga emas, balki uning rivojlanishi, takomillashuvi o‘z mohiyatini chuqurroq yuzaga chiqarish hisobiga yuz beradi”¹.

Milliylik, deb yozgan edi V.G. Belinskiy, “Yozuvchining xizmati emas balki ijodning shoir tomonidan uncha zo‘r berishni talab qilmaydigan zaruriy shartidir. Shuning uchun ham asar badiiy jihatdan qanchalik yuksak bo‘lsa, u shunchalar milliydir, ulug‘ san‘atkorni milliyliги uchun maqtash ulug‘ astronomni o‘z hisob-kitoblaridagi karra jadvalida adashmaganliги uchun maqtashday gap... milliylik shoirni ulug‘ qilmaydi, balki buyuk talent shoirni milliy qiladi... agarda asar badiiy bo‘lsa, u o‘z-o‘zidan milliy bo‘ladi”.

Asarlarda xalq ruhiyatini, ularning psixologiyasini, millatning milliy xarakterini, milliy urf-odatlarini ochib berish ham milliylikning bir bo‘lagidir. O‘tgan asrdagi

¹ www.arxiv.uz

adabiyotlarda keltirilishicha, oldinlari milliylik faqat asarning tilida namoyon bo‘ladi degan xulosa bo‘lgan hozirgi zamonaviy adabiyotda esa bu tushuncha eskirgan. Hozirgi zamonaviy adabiy jarayonda milliy xarakter yoki asarda milliylik kayfiyati bo‘lishi uchun faqat tilgina kerak emas. Badiiy asarning milliyliigi va umuminsoniyligi asarning tilidan tashqari unda keltirilgan badiiy tasvir vositalari, asarda keltirilgan milliy tafakkur, asarda keltirilgan geografik joylashuv va tabiiy sharoit kabi vositalarga ham bog‘liq.

Yuqorida asarda dialektlarning qo‘llanilishi, sheva va lahjalar haqida so‘z yuritganimizda, asarning milliyligini ta‘minlovchi asosiy vosita til ekanligiga guvoh bo‘lamiz. Tog‘ay Murod o‘z asarlaridagi milliylikni o‘zi tug‘ilib-o‘sgan joyning shevasi(tili) bilan ochib berishga harakat qildi. “Shevasiz tili, - degan edi folklorshunos olim Bahodir Sarimsoqov – eng shukuhsiz va jozibasiz til. Mana shu bois, o‘zbek ijodkorlari o‘z asarlaridagi til badiiyatini ta‘minlashda o‘zlari mansub bo‘lgan shevalarga murojaat etadilar”².

“Tog‘ay Murod asarlarida biz aniq o‘tgan zamon fe‘llaridan foydalanganligining guvohi bo‘lamiz. Aniq o‘tgan zamon fe‘li ma‘no jihatidan harakatning nutq so‘zlanib turgan paytdan nutq so‘zlanib turgan paytdan oldin bajarilganligini anglatadi. Bunda so‘zlovchi harakatning bajarilganligini ko‘rgandek yoki uning guvohi bo‘lgandek xabar qiladi. Aniq o‘tgan zamon fe‘llari o‘zlaridagi qo‘shimchalarning turli-tumanligi bilzn xarakterlanadi va bu jihatdan o‘tgan zamon fe‘llarining boshqa turlaridan ajralib turadi.

Bobomiz hovlisi Farg‘onada bo‘ladi.

Dalasi Farg‘ona adog‘ida bo‘ladi.

Bobomiz dalasi oldidan bir ariq suv oqadi.

Suv gavhar zilol-gavhar zilol suv bo‘ladi.

Suv egilmish tollar majnun-majnun sollaradi.

Bobomiz hovlisi Farg‘onada bo‘ladi – ish-harakat kelasi zamonda qo‘llanilmoqda. Lekin biz uni o‘qish jarayonida aniq o‘tgan zamon voqealariga guvoh bo‘lamiz. O‘zbek asabiy

² Sarimsoqov B. Badiiylik asoslari va mezonlari. – T.: S Ahmedova bosmaxonasi, 2004. – B.118

tilidagi singari, o‘zbek xalq shevalarida ham fe’ning zamon formalari xilma-xil bo‘lib, ular o‘ziga xos xarakterli tomonlarga egadir.

Bizningcha, bu jumlada fe’l zamonlari qanday formada berilishidan qat’iy nazar, ularni o‘tgan zamon formasida qabul qilishimiz o‘rinli bo‘lar edi”³, - deyiladi Abubakir O‘rozovning doktorlik dissertatsiyasida.

Marifat Qosimova O‘z tadqiqotlarida, badiiy asarda personaj nutqining fonetik o‘zgachaligi hamda uslubiy vositalarning qo‘llanishida qahramonning emotsional holatiga badiiy bo‘yoq berish, tasvir ta’sirchanligini oshirishda asar badiiyligini ta’minlovchi fonostilistik asoslardan biri deb hisoblaydi⁴.

Milliylik adibimiz Tog‘ay Murod asarlaridagi qahramonlarning nutqida ko‘p ishlatilgan maqol va matallarda yaqqolroq ko‘rinadi. L.N.Tolstoy ta’biri bilan aytganda, “har bir maqolda shu maqolni yaratgan xalqning siymosi ko‘rinadi”. Zero, xalq maqollari umuminsoniy g‘oyalarni milliy shaklda targ‘ib qiluvchi janr hisoblanadi. Ular odatda xalq madaniyati mahsulidir.

Tog‘ay Murod asarlarining boshqa yozuvchilarimizning asarlariga o‘xshamaydigan jihatlari juda ko‘p. ijodkorning uslubida, asarining tilida buni sezish qiyin emas, albatta. Uning o‘ziga xos yozuvchilik uslubi – nazmda bitilgan nasrga o‘xshaydi. Lekin she’rdagi kabi vazn, qofiya yo‘q. Jumalari qisqa, xalq tiliga yaqin, she’rdagi kabi tovush va so‘zlar ko‘p. uning asarlarini baxshilarimizning sodda ijodiga o‘xshatsa bo‘ladi. Ya’ni bir tomoni shundaki, milliy urf-odatlar, rasm-rusumlar, maqollar, so‘zlashish tarzi surxondaryocha uslubda namoyon bo‘ladi. Asardagi butun tasvir o‘zbek millatining qaysidir hududining qavmiga tegishli mahalliy tasvirdek namoyon bo‘ladi.

Pirimqul Qodirov o‘z xotiralarida shunday yozadi: “Tog‘ay Murod qissalari adabiyotimizga Surxon vodiysining o‘ziga xos nafasini olib kirdi, mehnatsevar, kamtar vat anti chorvadorlar, bog‘bonlarga nisbatan dilimizda samimiy mehr uyg‘otdi. “Ot kishnagan oqshom” qissasi “Alpomish” dostoni an’analarini eslatadigan xalqchil ruh bilan sug‘orilgan.

³ O‘rozov A. Tog‘ay Murod asarlarida milliy xarakter yaratish mahorati.

Filol. fanlari nomzodi ... diss. – T., 2021

⁴ Qosimova M. Badiiy nutq individualligining lingvistik xususiyatlari (Tog‘ay Murod asarlari asosida).

Filol. fanlari nomzodi ... diss. Avtoref. – T., 2007. – B.8.

Tog‘ay Murodning o‘zi ham Alpomish va Barchinlarni bergan go‘zal vodiylar, bepoyon yaylovlarda o‘sganliggi uning so‘z boyliklaridan, yozuvchilik uslubi va o‘ziga xos ovoizidan sezilib turadi. Nasriy asarga she‘riy jarang va ko‘tarini ruh bag‘ishlay olish qobiliyati yosh adibning qalamiga xos eng yaxshi fazilatlardandir”⁵.

“Shu ma’noda, xalqimizning turmush va tafakkur tarziga nazar tashlaydigan bo‘lsak, boshqalarga hech o‘xshamaydigan, ming yillar davomida shakllangan, nafaqat o‘zaro muomala, balki hayotimizning uzviy bir qismi sifatida namoyon bo‘ladigan bir qator o‘ziga xos xususiyatlarni ko‘ramiz. Misol uchun, tilimizdagi mehr-oqibat, mehr-muhabbat, mehr-shafqat, qadr-qimmat degan, bir-birini chuqur ma’no-mazmun bilan boyitadigan va to‘ldiradigan iboralarni olaylik. Qanchalik g‘alati tuyulmasin, bu iboralarni boshqa tillarga aynan tarjima qilishning o‘zi mushkul bir muammo. Shuni aytish lozimki, bu tushunchalar kimdir shunchaki o‘ylab topgan shirin kalom, quloqqa xush yoqadigan so‘zlar emas. Bunday tushunchalar asrlar mobaynida el-yurtimizning dunyoqarashi, ma’naviy hayotining negizi sifatida vujudga kelgan, ong-u shuurimizdan chuqur joy olgan buyuk qadriyatlarining amaliy ifodasidir”⁶.

Yozuvchimiz Tog‘ay Murod “Yulduzlar mangu yonadi” asarida Bo‘ri polvon yo‘qolib borayotgan qadriyatlarimizni bir-bir eslab turadi. Va yoshlarga shunday murojaat etadi:

“Avlodlar almashgan sayin... yo, pirim-e. tuf-tuf-tuf... avlodlar almashgan sayin... yurak yo‘qolib boryapti!

Jasad bor! Aql bor!

Yurak yo‘q!

To‘rt muchal bor! Kuch-quvvat Bor!

Yurak yo‘q!

⁵ Tog‘ay Murod. Oydinda yurgan odamlar. – T.: Adabiyot va san‘at, 1985. – B. 155

⁶ Karimov I. Yuksak ma’naviyat – yengilmas kuch. – T.: Ma’naviyat, 2008. B.8.

Ko'krakda jon bor!

Yurak yo'q, yurak!.. Farzandlar hayotga beparvo qaraydi. Musibat bilan xursandchilik farqiga bormaydi”⁷. “Tog‘ayning «Ot kishnagan oqshom» qissasi chop etilishida mening ham hissam borligini boya aytib o‘tgan edim. Uning asarlarida shira bor, milliylik bor, adibning aytadigan gaplari bor. «Ot kishnagan oqshom» qissasi Yo‘ldosh Oxunboboev nomidagi Yosh tomoshabinlar teatrida rejissyor Olimjon Salimovning instsenirovkasi bo‘yicha sahnaga qo‘yildi. Ba‘zilar aytishi mumkin: «Xo‘sh, nima bo‘pti, rejissyor o‘zi instsenirovka qildi, o‘zi qo‘ydi», deb. Yo‘q, agar asarning negizida gapi bo‘lmasa, rejissyor uni hech narsa qilolmaydi. «Xo‘p, olib chiqsa nima bo‘pti?!» — ham deyishar. Bizda nima ko‘p — sahna asari ko‘p. Shularning ichidan faqat Tog‘ayning asarini tanlab, qardosh Qozog‘iston Davlat akademik teatri o‘z sahnalarida qozoqchaga o‘girib gumburlatib qo‘yayotganiga nima deysiz? Bu tasodifmi? Yo‘q, bu tasodif emas. Asarda qozoq birodarlarimizga ma‘qul keladigan biror gapi borki, sahnalashtirgan. Shu paytgacha Abdulla Qahhorning «Og‘riq tishlar»i bilan Said Ahmadning «Kelinlar qo‘zg‘oloni» qozoq sahnasi yuzini ko‘rgan edi. Bular ilgarigi davrda edi. Tog‘ay Murodniki esa istiqlolimiz davriga to‘g‘ri keldi. Davr masalasini hisobga olsak, unda qardoshlar sahnasiga chiqqan bizning asarimiz yakkayu yagona shu Tog‘ay Murodniki bo‘lib qoladi. Shuning o‘zi ham ancha narsani anglatmaydimi, axir? Bu asar, demak, qardoshlarimizga ham ma‘qul bo‘libdi. Nimasi ma‘qul bo‘ldi ekan? Ma‘lumingizki, Qozog‘iston asosan chorvador respublika. Paxtachilik qanchalik bizning milliy xarakterimizni belgilaydigan bo‘lsa, ularda chorvachilik, chorva aksari xalqning kasb-korini belgilaydigan soha. Ot, qoramol, qo‘y, echki qozoqlarning joni. «Ot kishnagan oqshom» asari faqat ot kishnagani uchun emas, balki tasvirlanayotgan ob‘ektga munosabati bilan, odamlarning dardini haqqoniy ayta bilgani bilan ham qardoshlarimiz sahnasi yuzini ko‘rishga munosib deb topildi. Ba‘zan ba‘zan nega bizning adabiyotimiz jahonga chiqmaydi, deganga o‘xshagan gap-so‘zlar bo‘lib turadi. Jahonga chiqish uchun biz yaratgan asarlarda jahonshumul muammolar ko‘tarilishi, baquvvat-baquvvat qahramonlar yaratilishi kerak.

⁷ Tog‘ay Murod. Tanlangan asarlar. Yulduzlar mangu yonadi. – T.: Sharq, 2008 – J. I: - B.46

Men hech ikkilanmay aytishim mumkinki, Tog‘ay Murodning keyingi romanlari, agar malakali tarjimonning qo‘liga tushib, ko‘ngildagidek tarjima qilinsa, boshqa yurtlardagi o‘quvchilarning javonlaridan ham o‘rin olishi turgan gap. Men shu yoshga kirib shunga amin bo‘ldimki, yozuvchidan keyin uning asarlarini targ‘ib qiladigan kimdir qolishi kerak ekan. Mana, Ma’suma shu yo‘ldan borib jon kuydiryapti. Tog‘ay Murodning asarlarini chet tillarga tarjima qilib chop etilishi uchun ham uni qo‘llab-quvvatlab turadigan tashkilot, jonkuyar odam bo‘lishi kerak. Menimcha, uning asarlaridan biri xalqaro tillardan biriga tarjima qilinib chop etilsa bas, uyog‘ini asarning o‘zi tortib ketadi. Tog‘ay menga ukadek aziz, do‘stdek qadrdon edi. Nachora, Ollohning irodasi ekan, umri qisqa bo‘ldi. Yashab, ijod qilib yursa bo‘lardi. Afsuski, yaratgan Egam o‘zi berganini o‘zi oladi. Lekin Tog‘ay Murod ozgina yashagan bo‘lsa ham sozgina asarlar yaratib, o‘ziga haykal qo‘yib ketdi. Ukamizning joyi jannatda bo‘lsin”⁸!

Talabalik davrida kitob do‘konlarini aylanib, yangi nashr etilgan badiiy asarlarni xarid qilishga oshiqardik. Kunlarning birida «Ot kishnagan oqshom» kitobiga ko‘zim tushdi. Sarlavhasining o‘ziyoq e’tiborimni tortdi. Uyga kelib, asar mutolaasiga berildim. Aytish joizki, bu mening qissalar muallifi Tog‘ay Murod bilan ilk muloqotim, tanishuvim edi. Qissalarni o‘qir ekanman, unda yozuvchi borlig‘ini, qalb haroratini sezib turardim. Adib qalbidagi ehtiros asarlariga joziba, jon bag‘ishlagan edi. Xususan, uning inson botiniyu zohirini aniq-tiniq ifodalashi, tabiat nafosatini turfa rang, betakror ohangda yoritib berishi meni maftun etdi. Tog‘ay Murod ilk «Yulduzlar mangu yonadi» qissasida Bo‘ri polvon obrazi orqali imon-e’tiqod, or-nomusni talqin etdi. Men asarda kurash sahnasini, aniqrog‘i, davrasini zavq bilan tomosha qildim, polvonlar mardligi, g‘ururini yuksak qadrlashidan faxrlandim. Yozuvchi polvonlarning o‘zini uch balo: ayolbozlik, ichkilikbozlik, nafs balosidan asrashiga urg‘u berishida mantiq bor. Mazkur shartlar nafaqat polvonlarga, balki odamzotga, umumga taalluqli. Zero, bu illatlardan xoli insongina bu dunyoda halol, xotirjam kun kechiradi.

Tog‘ay Murod olam va odam uyg‘unligini «Ot kishnagan oqshom» qissasida Ziyodulla kal va Tarlon ot misolida badiiy tadqiq etgan. Adib otni ta’riflabgina qolmay, uni

⁸ Men qaytib kelaman. Tog‘ay Murod zamondoshlari xotirasida. – T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2007.

yorqin bo‘yoqlarda chizib beradi: «Tarlon dumlari yoyildi, yollari hurpaydi. Yollari bir chap bo‘ynida, bir o‘ng bo‘ynida o‘ynadi! Bu yol emas, ipak, ipak! Bu yol emas, do‘mbira tori, do‘mbira tori! Gajak-gajak bo‘yinlar bo‘yin emas, do‘mbira, do‘mbira!» Ziyodulla otni darddoshi, qadrdoni bilib sirlashishi, so‘zlashishi kishi ko‘ngliga epkinlik olib kiradi. Qissa o‘quvchida otga, atrof-olamga mehru muhabbat uyg‘otibgina qolmay, jonzotlar qalbini his qilishga o‘rgatadi. Asarlarini o‘qib, o‘zlashtirib borar ekanman, adib ijodining yangi qirralarini kashf qilishga intildim. «Oydinda yurgan odamlar» asarida yurak-yurakdan silqib chiqqan musiqani his qildim. Pok tuyg‘ularni oy jilosida jilvalantirgan muallif iste’dodiga tan berdim. Qoplon va Oymomo timsolida vafosadoqat, muhabbat, sabr-bardosh nozik ifodalangan. Adib milliy qadriyat, an’analarni asar ruhiga mohirona singdirib yuborgan. Garchi asarda mahzun ohang yetakchi bo‘lsada, har bir lavhada o‘zgacha tarovat mujassam: «Ko‘zlaringga boqishlarim... boqishlarimizning o‘zi bir doston, momosi. Bovujud shoirlar bilmadi, bilsa, elga yoyardi... Men senga aytsam, momosi, boqishlarda hali o‘zimizniki...» Qahramonning dil nomalari, sof muhabbati, ko‘ngil rozlari o‘quvchida lirik kayfiyat tug‘diradi. Tog‘ay Murod qissalaridagi aniq va izchil ifoda, musiqiylik, siqqlik, ma’no va ohang uyg‘unligi menda uning ijodiga katta qiziqish uyg‘otdi”⁹.

Taniqli adabiyotshunos olim Ibrohim G‘ofurov Tog‘ay Murod singari bir qator yozuvchilar ijodi haqida to‘xtalib, ular ijodining umumiy va alohida tomonlarini bayon qilgan edi: “...Ular o‘z temalarini, hayotini yoritish uslub, yo‘sinlarini topib olganlar. Ularnig ijodi o‘ziga xos yo‘llardan o‘sib borayotganligini hech kim inkor etmaydi. Keyingi yillar ichida ularning asarlari va yaratgan qahramonlari, uslubiy izlanishlari xususida bo‘lib o‘tayotgan qizg‘in bahslar va ularda ochilayotgan adabiy haqiqatlar shundan dalolat bermoqda. Ular adabiyotimizga vijdoni g‘alayonda bo‘lgan inson obrazlarini olib kirishga intilmoqdalar. Bu ularning yutuqlari ham, yo‘qotishlari ham oz emas...

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Эффективность проведения комплексной судебной экспертизы для различных объектов

Аннотация: Речь в данной статье ведётся о роли комплексных экспертиз в дальнейшем улучшении качественных показателей исследований, проводимых с целью укрепления результатов новых исканий в сфере улучшения качества исследований, проводимых в судебно-экспертной деятельности, и усиления их эффективности в раскрытии преступлений.

Ключевые слова: исследование, экспертиза, комплекс, специалист, квалификация, объекты исследования, микрообъекты.

На сегодняшний день в Республике Узбекистан впечатляет масштаб мер и мероприятий проводимых с целью интенсивного развития судебно-экспертной деятельности. С целью улучшения качества исследований, проводимых в судебно-экспертной деятельности и усиления их эффективности в расследовании преступлений, в данную сферу также внедряются результаты всё более новых достижений и изысканий.

В нашей стране ежедневно, ежечасно осуществляются непрерывные исследования и активные изыскания, направленные на коренное модернизирование и обновление всех сфер и систем жизнедеятельности. Не осталось ни одного направления, ни одной сферы, которые бы не затронули и не изменили их суть, широкомасштабные реформы, направленные на улучшение качества жизни населения.

Некоторые вопросы, решаемые путём проведения экспертизы, носят комплексный характер, информация и результаты, получаемые во время их проведения, напрямую зависят от практического опыта и профессиональной квалификации специалиста-эксперта.

Комплексная экспертиза- это комплекс исследований, проводимых при участии двух или более экспертов, то есть, исследования, проводимые в отношении одного объекта в результате назначения нескольких видов экспертизы. Подобное можно встретить при назначении в отношении одного объекта традиционного или

нетрадиционного вида экспертиз, к примеру, для исследования предоставлен один документ, и в случае, если в отношении него возникают вопросы, касающиеся криминалистического исследования почерковедческой экспертизы, в этом случае назначаются два вида экспертизы.

С целью устранения проблем, возникающих в организации деятельности экспертов-трасологов, по некоторым видам трасологической экспертизы необходимов назначение комплексной экспертизы (идентификация целого по его частям, исследования редко встречающихся следов, а также следов производственного механизма на продукции, следов механических повреждений на замках, пломбах и одежде). Часто именно в данных видах экспертизы перед экспертом-трасологом могут ставиться вопросы, находящиеся вне пределов его компетенции.

На сегодняшний день в нашей республике существует более 60-ти видов экспертизы, которые требуют комплексного изучения направлений, связанных не только с уголовным, гражданским или административным законодательством, но и с новыми развивающимися видами дисциплин относительно семьи, экологии и др.. В данном направлении необходимо соблюдение конкретных требований на стадии предварительного и судебного следствия, предъявляемых к органам дознания и следственным органам на этапах работы на месте происшествия, его осмотра, подготовки к назначению экспертизы. В данном ряду требований нужно также отметить необходимость фиксации микроследов, возможных к предоставлению для трасологической экспертизы.

Как известно, криминалистическая дисциплина изучает в том числе и следы, и особое место в ней занимают различные следы очень малой величины (пыль, комки почвы, различные натуральные и синтетические волокна, биологические частицы искусственного и естественного происхождения, соскобы с лакокрасочных покрытий, и т.п.). В случае, если данные материальные объекты, микрочастицы (микрообъекты) находятся в причинной связи с уголовным происшествием, то есть хранят в себе информацию о подготовке, совершении преступления, или о своём

возникновении в результате сокрытия преступления, с криминалистической точки зрения данные микрообъекты считаются следами.

На наш взгляд, что в список трасологических следов необходимо также включить микроотпечатки и микрообъекты, поскольку это позволяет назначить комплексную экспертизу при проведении трасологических исследований и создаёт ряд облегчений при раскрытии преступлений по микрообъектам, полученным в ходе осмотра места происшествия.

Комплексную экспертизу можно назначать также при проведении трасологических исследований следов обуви, в частности, в случае наличия на следах веществ, схожих с пятнами крови или частиц почвы, можно решить задачу путём формирования диагностических вопросов относительно данных веществ.

Комплексную экспертизу можно также назначать еще в одном виде трасологических исследований- относительно следов механических повреждений, оставшихся на одежде и идентификации целого по его частям, однако необходимо отметить, что данный вид исследований наиболее важен для микроотпечатков и микрообъектов. Поэтому при проведении трасологической экспертизы необходимо не только совершенствовать комплексные экспертизы, но и принимать во внимание исследования микроотпечатков и микрообъектов.

Необходимо отметить, что в криминалистике микрообъектами могут являться образования с различной природой происхождения. К их числу относятся микроволокна, частицы лакокрасочных материалов покрытий, осколки стекла, частицы наркотических веществ, различные биологические выделения, и т.п.. Они различаются между собой не только по своей природе, но и по своему внешнему и внутреннему строению, особенностям криминалистических признаков, степени выраженности морфологических признаков, возможности фиксации и получения без изменения своих свойств и характеристик.

Также, с учётом широкого круга трасологических объектов, в первую очередь необходимо сформировать сборник вопросов, которые будут ставиться перед проведением комплексной экспертизы, так как не всегда в отношении объектов, предъявляемых для исследования, ставятся прямые и конкретные вопросы, что, в

свою очередь, значительно снижает эффективность исследований и возможность получения точной информации.

При проведении трасологических экспертиз, уточнив виды объектов и список вопросов, которые могут быть поставлены перед экспертами, необходимо также принять во внимание круг знаний специалистов, который будет необходим для осуществления данного процесса.

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Isroil-falastin mojarosi Falastin turizm sanoati misolida.

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola Isroil-Falastin mojarosi va uning Falastin turizm sanoatiga ta'siri bilan bog'liq murakkab munosabatlarni o'rganishga qaratilgan. Mintaqaning boy madaniy va tarixiy merosi uni sayyohlar uchun muhim turistik manzilga aylantirishi mumkin bo'lsa-da, davom etayotgan ziddiyat uning salohiyatini sezilarli darajada pasaytiradi. Mazkur maqolada ushbu murakkab ssenariyga hissa qo'shayotgan siyosiy, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy jihatlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, turistik manzil, isroil-falastin mojarosi, G'arbiy Sohil, bosib olingan hududlar, noqonuniy aholi punktlari, blokada, yahudiylar, falastinliklar

2017 yilda Jahon sayyohlik tashkiloti tomonidan eng tez o'sayotgan sayyohlik yo'nalishi sifatida qayd etilgan Falastin (Amar, 2017), Isroil bilan o'rtadagi nizoga qaramasdan, xalqaro sayyohlar orasida tobora mashhurlikka erishmoqda. Uchta yakkaxudolik dinlarining muqaddas zamini sizni "Musos, Iso va Muhammadning izidan yurishga" (Griffoulieres, 2016) taklif qiladi.

Falastin dunyoga o'zini ham tarixiy yer, ham ruhiy-ma'naviy markaz, ham geografik xilma-xil o'lka sifatida tanishtiradi (Laura, 2016). Falastinga sayohat, shuningdek, isroil-falastin mojarosini yaqindan tushunish uchun noyob imkoniyatdir. Biroq, e'tiborga olish kerak bo'lgan bir qancha omillar mavjud. Xususan, sayyohdan sayohatga yaxshi tayyorgarlik ko'rishi va Falastinda bo'lishi davomida yuzaga keladigan har qanday to'siqlarga tayyor bo'lishi so'raladi. (Pareeag, 2018)

Quddus, Vifleyim va Jeriko shaharlari bo'ylab sayohat taklif qilayotgan mahalliy sayyohlik agentligi "Yangi yerlar" : "Ko'pchilik o'ylashi mumkin bo'lgan fikrlardan farqli o'laroq, Falastin sayohatchi o'zini to'liq xavfsizlikda his qiladigan joy", - deya ishontirmoqda (Ayman, 2020). Bundan tashqari Jenin, Nabluz, Qumron, Xebron va Ramalla

kabi qadimiy shaharlar tashrif buyuruvchilar uchun ajoyib sayohat imkoniyatlarini taklif qiladi (Griffoulieres, 2016). Jumladan, Vifleyimga dunyoning turli burchaklaridan sayyohlar, boshqa narsalar qatori, Iso payg'ambar tug'ilgan joyda qurilgan Tug'ilish cherkovini ziyorat qilish uchun kelishadi. Bu yerda, shuningdek, biz Isroil va Falastin o'rtasidagi murakkab hududiy vaziyatning oqibati bo'lgan mashhur Isroil ajratish devori (West Bank barrier) ni ko'rishimiz mumkin (Thielin, 2019).

Falastinga sayohatni Quddussiz tasavvur etib bo'lmaydi. Uchta yirik dinning muqaddas shahri bo'lgan Quddusga ham isroilliklar, ham falastinliklar da'vo qilishadi. Shaharning sharqiy qismi Falastinga tegishli, g'arbiy qismi esa Isroilniki hisoblanadi. (Griffoulieres, 2017). Gap shundaki, shaharning Falastinga tegishli qismida barcha eng muhim muqaddas joylar, jumladan, musulmonlar uchun Al-Aqso masjidi, yahudiylar uchun Dovud shahri va G'arbiy devor, nasroniylar uchun esa Ma'bad tog'i mavjud (LO, 2017).

Yuqorida takidlanganidek, Falastinda borib ko'rish mumkin bo'lgan joylar juda ko'p. Shunga qaramay, nafaqat sayohatchi, balki Falastin turizm sanoati uchun ham turli qiyinchiliklar mavjud. Birinchidan, Isroil-Falastin mojarosi Falastindagi turizmga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Ko'pgina tarixiy obidalarni bosib olingan Falastin hududlarida, G'arbiy Sohilda va Sharqiy Quddusda topish mumkin. G'azo sektori blokadada bo'lganligi sababli unga kirishning imkoni yo'q (Laura, 2016). Shuning uchun sayyoh u yerga borishdan oldin mintaqadagi siyosiy iqlim haqida bilib olishi kerak. Bu yerga yetib kelgach u ko'plab nazorat punktlari va yo'llarda sabr-toqatli bo'lishi kerak (Pareeag, 2018). Ikkinchidan, G'arbiy Sohil va Sharqiy Quddusdagi noqonuniy aholi punktlarining kengayishi "ikki davlat" yechimini, shuningdek, Falastin turizm sanoatining mavjud bo'lishini xavf ostiga qo'yimoqda (Ismail, 2020). Bosib olingan hududlarda falastinliklar va ko'chib kelgan yahudiylar o'rtasidagi to'qnashuvlar ehtimoldan holi emas. Shu sababli sayyohlarga bir nechta ehtiyotkorlik qoidalariga rioya qilish tavsiya etiladi: hamma joyga bormaslik, namoyishlardan qochish, o'z davlatlarining elchixonasi yoki konsulligi bilan aloqada bo'lish va hokazo (Griffoulieres, 2016).

Falastinga faqatgina Isroil orqali borish mumkin (Amar, 2017). Salbiy tomoni shundaki, pasportda Isroil muhrining bo'lishi dunyoning ayrim Falastin masalasi bilan

birdam bo'lgan mamlakatlari : Livan, Jazoir yoki Eronga kirish huquqidan mahrum qiladi (Laura, 2016). Shuningdek, Isroilga boradigan sayyoh mamlakatga kirish sabablari haqida savol berishdan qochib qutula olmaydi. Eng muhimi, Falastinga tashrif buyurish to'g'risida og'iz ochmaslik lozim. Bu to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ortga qaytarilishni anglatishi mumkin (Camille, 2019).

Falastindagi turizm haqida gapirish birmuncha mintaqaning geosiyosiy holatini bilishni talab qiladi. Isroil-Falastin mojarosining sabablarini so'roq qilmasdan Falastinga sayohat taklif qiladigan sayyohlik kompaniyalari bunday nozik mavzuda jiddiy xatolikka yo'l qo'yishi mumkin. Xalqaro Amnistiya tashkiloti, masalan, o'zining 2019-yil 30-yanvardagi hisobotida TripAdvisor, Booking.com, Expedia, Airbnb kabi turizmga ixtisoslashgan raqamli kompaniyalarni Isroil bosib olgan Falastin hududlarida mehmonxonalar, mehmon uylari, tadbirlar va sayohatlar taklif qilish orqali urush jinoyatlaridan foyda olishda aybladi (International, 2019).

Albatta, mustamlakachilik Falastin xalqining o'z taqdirini o'zi belgilashiga jiddiy xavf tug'diradi. Bundan tashqari, u falastinliklarning madaniy va tabiiy obidalarga kirish hamda ulardan foydalanish huquqini rad etadi. Isroil uchun turizm noqonuniy aholi punktlarini Isroilning tarixiy obidalari deb da'vo qilish va Injilga asoslangan diniy turizmni tashkil etish orqali ularni Isroil hududi sifatida qonuniylashtirish uchun imkon beradi (Ahmad, 2020).

Gap shundaki, Falastin hukumati faqat G'arbiy Sohilning bir qismida hokimiyatga ega, G'azo sektorini esa Xamas boshqaradi (Leclerc, 2020). Bu esa vaziyatni yanada murakkablashtiradi. Oslo kelishuvlariga ko'ra, G'arbiy Sohil uchta hududga bo'lingan: A, B va C. A hududi faqat Falastin ma'muriyati tomonidan nazorat qilinadi. B hududi Falastin ma'muriyati va Isroilning birgalikda nazorati ostida. G'arbiy sohilning 60 foizini tashkil etuvchi C zonasi esa faqat Isroil nazorati ostida (Oxfam, 2017). Aytish kerakki, Oslo kelishuvlari B va C zonalarini falastinliklarga bosqichma-bosqich o'tkazishni nazarda tutar edi. (Oxfam, 2017) Biroq, Oslo kelishuvlaridan falastinliklar olgan yagona narsa bu kolonizatsiya bo'ldi (Kriegel, 2020).

Bosib olingan hududlarda Isroil o‘z qonuni va hokimiyatini o‘rnatib, o‘z bilganicha harakat qilmoqda. Jumladan, Falastin avtomobillarining Isroilga, Sharqiy Quddusga, Isroil kuchlari nazorati ostidagi G‘arbiy Sohildagi ayrim sayyohlik joylariga kirishi taqiqlangan. Bundan tashqari, Falastin avtomobillari G‘azo va G‘arbiy Sohil o‘rtasida harakatlana olmaydi va G‘arbiy Sohildagi ko‘plab yo‘llarga cheklangan kirish imkoniyatiga ega (Department, 2017). Isroil nafaqat G‘arbiy Sohilga, yoki Sharqiy Quddus va G‘azo sektoriga kirish, balki yer va resurslar, jumladan, suv, haydaladigan yerlar, telekommunikatsiya va elektr uzatish liniyalari, O‘lik dengiz va “C” hududida joylashgan barcha arxeologik yodgorliklar ustidan nazorat qiladi. (Departament, 2017) Shubhasiz, bu Isroilga falastinliklarni xohlagancha manipulyatsiya qilish imkonini beradi.

Isroil o‘z ixtiyori bilan bosib olingan hududlardan turizm maqsadlarida foydalanmoqda. Egallab olingan Sharqiy Quddusda qurilgan Quddus devorlari milliy bog‘i, shuningdek, “Injil aylanmasi” Sharqiy Quddusdagi falastinliklarning uylarini buzish uchun bahona bo‘ldi (Ahmad, 2020). Yana bir joy - Tel Shilo bo‘lib, u yerda Bibliya mavzulari asosida qurilgan bog‘ har yili o‘n minglab sayyohlarni jalb qiladi. Isroilning ushbu obyektlarni diniy turizm uchun o‘zlashtirishi - bosib olingan Quddusdagi boshqa ko‘plab joylar, masalan, Dovud shahri, Zaytun tog‘i va Eski shaharga qo‘shimcha ravishda - yahudiylarning shu joyga abadiy mansubligi haqidagi sionistik hikoyalarga asoslanadi (Ahmad, 2020).

Isroil tomonidan kiritilgan cheklovlarga qaramay, Falastin o‘z hududiga nisbatan huquqlaridan foydalanishi uchun barcha imkoniyatlarni ishga solmoqda. Shunday qilib, u 2011 yilda Yuneskonning to‘liq a‘zosi bo‘ldi (Tessier, 2011). Bu, shubhasiz, Isroil ma‘qullamaydigan va falastinliklarning mojaroni davom ettirishga qaratilgan qadami deb biladigan qaror. Har holda bu qarorni xalqaro miqyosda Falastinni davlat sifatida tan olish yo‘lidagi oldinga qadam sifatida ko‘rish mumkin. Biroq, Isroil o‘zini tinchlik muzokaralariga tayyor qilib ko‘rsatsa ham, uning yonida yangi davlat paydo bo‘lishini istamasligi aniq. Aksincha, u Falastinning o‘z huquqlarini tiklashga qaratilgan urinishlariga qarshi qarshi choralar ko‘rayotganga o‘xshaydi. Shunday qilib, Isroil bosib olingan Falastin hududlari ustidan hech qanday huquqqa ega emasligini e‘lon qilgan va Sharqiy Quddusda

olib boriladigan ishlarni taqiqlashni so‘ragan Yunesko bilan munosabatlarini uzdi (Dubessy, 2016).

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, Falastin turizmi juda cheklangan va Isroil-Falastin mojarosi hal etilmaguncha shunday bo‘lib qoladi. Falastinga tashrif buyurishni istagan sayohatchilar, shuningdek, Falastin sayyohlik agentliklari Falastin hududlari mustamlaka qilinishi sababli ko‘plab cheklovlarga duch kelishmoqda. Isroil esa turizmni rivojlantirish uchun yerlar va tarixiy obidalarni o‘zlashtirib olishda erkin harakat qilmoqda. U bosib olingan yerlarga qonuniylik berish uchun turizmdan, ayniqsa diniy turizmdan foydalanadi. U Falastin bilan imzolangan kelishuvlarni ham, ikki davlat o‘rtasidagi iqtisodiy munosabatlarni tartibga soluvchi Parij protokolini ham hurmat qilmaydi (International, 2019). Falastin, o‘z navbatida, Isroil bilan muzokaralarda teng rol o‘ynash imkonini beradigan xalqaro tan olinish uchun kurashmoqda. Afsuski, Yunesko kabi xalqaro tashkilotlarning ovozi bilan Isroilga bosim o‘tkazishga bo‘lgan harakatlar natija berayotgani yo‘q. Faqatgina Isroilga qarshi qattiq xalqaro bosim Falastin va Isroil o‘rtasida tinchlik o‘rnatishga imkon berishi mumkin. Ana shunda Falastin davlati nihoyat xavfsiz va belgilangan chegaralar ichida o‘rnatilishi mumkin. Shundagina u barcha sohalar qatori turizmni mustaqil rivojlantirish imkoniga ega bo‘ladi.

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MODIFICATION ADDITIVES FOR HIGH-STRENGTH CONCRETE

Norboev Azizbek Akromjon ugli

Abstract. The article presents the results of research on the creation of a high-strength cement composite using a complex additive. The optimal concentrations of additives of the hyperplasticizer Odolit-K in combination with bentonite were determined.

Keywords: cement, Odolit-K, bentonite, hyperplasticizers, X-ray phase studies, surface, elasticity, concentration.

INTRODUCTION

In connection with the intensive development of high-rise construction, one of the main and priority directions in the field of building materials science is the production of high-strength cement composites using ordinary cements [1-3]. The main advantages of using these concretes are their improved mechanical and operational properties, the relative ease of the resulting structures, the reduction in the labor intensity of their production, the saving of reinforcement, and the comparative ease of creating architectural forms [4,5]. Despite these advantages, there are also a number of disadvantages associated with the relatively high consumption of the cement component, as well as the absence of a rigid stone skeleton. In addition, too high specific surface area of fine-grained concrete components due to high water demand leads to increased shrinkage deformations and deterioration of the structure. These disadvantages significantly limit the scope of application of fine-grained concrete.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are various methods that improve the quality of fine-grained concrete, where modifiers play the main role [3]. Concretes produced using chemical additives do not always and fully satisfy the high requirements of materials approved for use in the construction of modern critical buildings and structures.

Reducing the cost of manufactured products and obtaining building materials using highly effective surfactants of domestic production in combination with natural materials in concrete mixtures is an urgent task.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following materials were used in the presented work: hyperplasticizer Odolit-K, country of origin: C3S-62.13; C2S-16.15; C3A-7.42; C4AF-12.56. The chemical composition of cement is presented in Table 1;

Table 1.

Chemical composition of cement

Содержание оксидов						
SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	K ₂ O	SO ₃	MgO
21,96	5,45	4,13	66,71		1,75	

table 2

Chemical composition of bentonite

Содержание оксидов							
CO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	SiO ₂	MgO
12,1	17,4	20,0	2,1	2,4	1,3	41,7	3,1

Water for preparing samples was prepared as follows: the water was weighed, and the amount of bentonite was determined by calculating the concentration of the component and thoroughly mixed on a PE-6110 magnetic stirrer for 1 min. The resulting suspension was subjected to ultrasonic treatment on an IL100-6/2 ultrasonic unit for 15 seconds.

As a result of the introduction of powdered natural bentonite (Table 3), the compressive strength of the studied samples differs slightly from the control sample (composition 1). In this case, the maximum value of density and strength of the concrete samples under study is achieved in the range of bentonite concentrations of 2.28 - 3.38% in water. In this case, the percentage of bentonite per weight of cement is 0.4-0.6% by weight of cement.

Table 3

No.	Cement	Odolite-K, wt.% from cement	Concentration of bentonite powder, wt.% from cement	Surface tension mN/m	Normal density (NG), %	Density of cement stone, g/cm ³	Strength, MPa
1	500			72,7	23,25	2,18	112,5
2	500		0,4	67,1	23,25	2,2	121,9
3	500		0,6	62	24,2	2,16	120,5
4	500		0,8	60,1	25,3	2,16	114,3
5	500		1,0	72	26,8	2,11	114,8
6	500	0,6		60,51	21,2	2,32	132,9
7	500	1,0		51,26	20,00	2,32	131,3
8	500	1,4		49,92	18,75	2,35	133,6
9	500	1,0	0,4	49,6	17,75	2,39	136,8
10	500	1,0	0,6	48,4	17,8	2,35	137,1
11	500	1,0	1,0	48,1	17,3	2,34	138,8
12	500	1,4	1,0	48,1	17,5	2,35	138,1

At the same time, the normal density of cement paste with the introduction of 0.6% bentonite increases by 4%, and the strength of the cement stone increases by 7%. When bentonite is used in combination with Odolit - K, the value of normal density differs from the control by 24%, a more intensive reduction of the liquid phase is noted in cement paste. This distinctive feature obviously manifests itself as a result of a decrease in the surface tension of the dispersion medium in the cement paste with the combined use of a hyperplasticizer and bentonite clay, as reported by the authors of this work [2]. With the combined use of Odolit-K with bentonite, the maximum decrease in the surface tension of water was 48.1 mN/m (34%), while the normal density of the cement paste prepared with this water was 17.3%. This means a reduction in the water-cement ratio by 34.4%. At the same time, the increase in the strength of cement stone was 26.3%. Analyzing changes in the surface tension of water in the presence of the complex additive Odolit-K - bentonite 34%, a change in the normal density of cement paste 34.4%, we can state the existence of a direct relationship between these values. The Odolit-K additive was studied by other authors, and the results of normal density obtained by the authors of this work coincide with the results from work [5].

CONCLUSION

Analysis of the data obtained during the study of high-strength cement composites based on the complex additive Odolit-K and bentonite showed that the resulting concrete

differs from the control concrete obtained without the use of additives in its high strength, elasticity and high ultimate elongation.

A formulation of high-strength fine-grained concrete with high ultimate deformability has been developed.

Based on the above, the formulation of the resulting high-strength cement composite can be used in the design and construction of thin-walled building structures in earthquake-resistant construction.

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JUSTIFICATION FOR THE USE OF BIOCONCRETE FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF HYDRAULIC STRUCTURES

Norboev Azizbek Akromjon ugli

Abstract. Innovative building materials for the construction of hydraulic structures are presented, namely, self-healing concrete - a new stage in the development of building materials. The new self-healing concrete differs from classical recipes by adding fungi and bacterial spores to the composition, which can survive in alkaline conditions and give the building material new properties.

Keywords: Construction Materials, hydraulic structures, self-healing concrete, bioconcrete.

INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a building material that, in its liquid state, has the fluidity of water, which makes it possible to pour cement mortar into any shapes and niches 1 . In its hardened state, concrete has the hardness of stone, which makes it indispensable in the construction of large objects (bridges, high-rise buildings, dams, etc.). Moisture, temperature changes, exposure to chemicals, and corrosion have a destructive effect on concrete; over time, the material tends to dry out. Self-healing concrete is characterized by higher resistance to the influence of external destructive factors and has the property of self-healing [1–4].

Concrete is a durable building material that has the necessary properties for the construction of both large structures (bridges, overpasses, dams at hydroelectric power stations, etc.) and small construction products (curbs, street lighting masts, reinforced concrete fences, etc.).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the first time, the use of self-healing concrete was proposed by Henk Jonkers from the Netherlands Delft University of Technology, who managed to introduce bacteria of the genus bacilli into concrete, which can exist for decades in an alkaline environment. As a result, it was possible to add to the strength of concrete and reinforced concrete structures

the ability to self-heal and heal cracks [3]. Moreover, bacteria remain in a “dormant” state for a long time. When cracks form and moisture gets inside the structure, bacteria act actively. However, during a series of experiments, scientists were able to establish two problems: bacteria do not take root well on the surface of already built structures, cement poses a danger to bacteria, therefore, special microcapsules with nutrients for bacteria should be added to concrete, in which they can live for a long time . This circumstance, of course, increases capital costs in the production of concrete, but significantly reduces operating costs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The newest building materials discussed in this work are promising and will soon become increasingly popular among designers, builders and direct users. These materials are unique and technologically complex to produce, but their price-quality ratio is justified, but rather in the long term, since their service life is much longer. By using these materials in construction production, we significantly expand our capabilities and ease of use of the constructed objects, while in price they do not differ so significantly from their usual analogues. In addition, the construction industry, as one of the most resource-intensive, must develop in accordance with the requirements of the time and become more and more knowledge-intensive, including in the development of building materials.

Table 1

Estimated costing for the production of 1 m3 of precast concrete class B15

Name of components	Consumption rate
Portland cement, t	0,490
Crushed stone, m3	0,909
Sand, m3	0,899
Additive SP JK-08, kg	2,079
Water, m3	0,170
Total	

In addition to the listed costs, it is necessary to take into account the fact that during the period of reconstruction of concrete structures, as a rule, all work at the enterprise is stopped due to the complexity of the work. Therefore, the search for solutions for automatic sealing of cracks with self-healing mixtures becomes relevant. When conducting a feasibility study, it is impossible not to take into account the significant advantage of bioconcrete - the elimination of cracks and cracks without the use of special machines and

mechanisms, as well as its absolute environmental friendliness. The only waste product of bacteria is calcium carbonate, which completely dissolves in building structures without entering the environment.

Figure 1. Comparative analysis of the application of technologies for the production of self-healing concrete

CONCLUSION

Thus, the use of bioconcrete makes it possible to increase the resistance of concrete and reinforced concrete to adverse environmental conditions, as well as significantly reduce the costs of reconstruction of structures. Despite the increase in capital investments, the proposed technology is effective by increasing the durability of the structure, obtaining a new material with improved physical and chemical properties and reducing operating costs. This area of research is very promising; the potential profit from the use of such concrete in hydraulic structures is enormous.

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FUNCTIONAL ACTIVITY IN THE COMPOSITION OF AN ADDITIVE TO BIO- CONCRETE

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Abstract. The work investigated bioadditives to concrete based on immobilized bacteria *Bacillus licheniformis*. Drying options and the state of microorganisms during immobilization affect their functional activity in the composition of the biological product. The addition of biological products with freeze-dried spores and cells immobilized on diatomite into the cement mixture significantly improves the strength characteristics of the cement stone.

Keywords: microorganisms, bioconcrete, biomineralizationb method.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the idea of rational environmental management is becoming increasingly relevant, because The increase in consumption of the planet's resources by humanity leads to many environmental crises and climate change. Reducing the consumption of materials and increasing the service life of products, the production of which emits large amounts of greenhouse gases, are becoming absolute priorities in economic activity. A significant contribution to global man-made greenhouse gas emissions around the world is made by the production and use of concrete. The production of cement, the main component of concrete, produces 5% of anthropogenic carbon dioxide [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is impossible to refuse the use of concrete, since it is the most popular building material in the world, which is widely used in various structures due to its low cost and flexibility of properties depending on the additives used. Concrete structures can be cast in a variety of shapes and sizes, based on solving the required problems in the construction of certain buildings and infrastructure. Global concrete consumption is expected to rise to 3.7–4.4 billion tons by 2050 as the construction industry grows by 0.8–1.2% annually [2]. The need to develop new technologies to increase the service life of concrete structures is

recognized throughout the world. An additional beneficial effect on the environment from the introduction of new technologies will be a reduction in the development of new quarries for the extraction of gravel, limestone, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The service life of concrete structures can be significantly extended by sealing cracks that appear in it over time, the formation of which leads to general cracking of the structure. In the future, the tightness is broken, which is why water can get inside and corrosion of the metal fittings can begin. This can be avoided if you use concrete with the addition of microorganisms, which over time can “heal” cracks that form in concrete structures during operation.

Microorganisms can also improve the properties of concrete even at the hardening stage due to accelerating the hardening process of cement paste, increasing the intensity of the formation of calcite and aragonite crystals, and reducing the proportion of air cavities that are replaced by minerals [3].

The search for microorganisms that are able to precipitate CaCO_3 , survive and reproduce at the alkaline pH of concrete, and also form spores that are resistant to unfavorable environments is a key task in the production of bioconcrete. These criteria are met by spore-forming bacteria of the genus *Bacillus*, which can survive at high pH, have high urease activity, and the ability to biomineralize [4].

Concrete with such characteristics is applicable in structures where it is difficult to regularly inspect the condition of concrete structures, as well as where repairing newly formed cracks is very difficult or practically impossible. These are, for example, underground tunnels, dams and other water structures, bridges and overpasses, high-rise buildings that require large quantities of high-quality concrete. In these cases, the use of concrete with improved strength characteristics, greater durability, and the ability to self-heal may be economically feasible.

During the study, microorganisms with high urease activity were isolated. Isolation was carried out on Christensen's medium of the following composition, g/l: NaCl – 5, urea – 20, KH_2PO_4 – 1.2, glucose – 1, peptone – 2, pH 6.6–6.8; distilled water. To obtain an

indicator medium (assessment of urease activity), an aqueous solution of phenol red was added to a final concentration of 0.012 g/l.

The objects of the study were the bacteria *Bacillus licheniformis*, isolated from Lake Alykes (Greece) (B11) and Lake Pomorie (Bulgaria) (B12).

Further research was aimed at preparing a functional additive for concrete. Previous work has noted that different bacterial forms used in the bioadditive have different effects on the characteristics of the final cement paste. It was noted that preparations from cells of microorganisms that are just beginning to form spores can significantly improve the quality of cement compared to preparations from spores. In practice, immobilized forms of biological products are convenient. Immobilized forms are promising due to increased safety of cells/spores and ease of transportation of the drug. In the present study, diatomaceous earth was used for immobilization, which has good affinity for concrete and a high degree of sorption of bacterial cells.

The resulting biomass of microorganisms was immobilized on diatomite produced by Diatom Plant LLC to obtain the required concentration of cells in the preparation: diatomite was added to a concentrated suspension of cells/spores based on the culture liquid and thoroughly mixed, spores and cells were effectively adsorbed on the diatomite.

The resulting immobilized preparations were dried in different ways: some of them were dried at 37 °C in a layer 3-5 mm thick for 12-18 hours, and some were freeze-dried. Freeze drying of the samples was carried out using a CoolSafe 55-4 unit (ScanVak, Denmark). The samples were pre-frozen for 12 hours at a temperature of -70 °C, after which the system was evacuated (30 Pa). When drying, the following shelf heating modes were used: the shelves were not heated for 12 hours; For 6 hours the shelf temperature was maintained at 5 °C; 6 hours – 10 °C; 6 hours – 15 °C.

In the experiments, immobilized preparations with spores and cells at the stage of sporulation of *Bacillus licheniformis* bacteria (B11 and B12) were used with initial concentrations of microorganisms of 10⁷ and 10⁸ CFU/g of biological preparation, dried in a thin layer and freeze-dried.

CONCLUSION

The experiments show the potential of adding a biological product based on the bacteria *Bacillus licheniformis* to the cement mixture at the mixing stage. Experimental data showed that the use of microorganisms immobilized on diatomite increased the strength of cement stone by an average of 33% in bending and by 39% in compression compared to the control after seven days of hardening. An increase in the concentration of spores/cells in the biological product from 10^7 to 10^8 CFU/g did not lead to a significant increase in the strength properties of the cement stone.

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